

SATISFACTORY

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The SatisFactory project consortium is composed of:

CERTH¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA²	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy
QPLAN	Q-PLAN International Advisors LTD	Greece

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¹ Project Coordinator

² Terminated beneficiary since June 2016 and replaced by QPLAN

AUTHORS LIST

Leading Author (Editor)				
	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
	Radogna	Daniele	REGOLA	d.radogna@regola.it
Co-authors (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Arena	Damiano	EPFL	damiano.arena@epfl.ch
2	Chatzikontidou	Anastasia	ABE	chatzikontidou@abe.gr
3	Dontsiou	Maria	ABE	dontsiou@abe.gr
4	Ensianli	Katerina	ABE	elsianli@abe.gr
5	Efremidis	Dimitrios	ABE	de@abe.gr
6	Fiore	Davide	REGOLA	d.fiore@regola.it
7	Georgopoulos	Georgios	ATLANTIS	georgopoulos@abe.gr
8	Ippolito	Massimo	COMAU	massimo.ippolito@comau.com
9	Mochament	Konstantinos	CERTH	k.mochament@iti.gr
10	Papadopoulos	Nikolaos	ABE	n.papadopoulos@abe.gr
11	Putero	Michele	COMAU	michele.putero@comau.com
12	Sforza	Aldo	REGOLA	a.sforza@regola.it
13	Tsakiris	Athanasios	CERTH	atsakir@iti.gr
14	Turinetto	Maurizio	REGOLA	m.turinetto@regola.it
15	Vamvalis	Cosmas	ABE	vamvalis@abe.gr
16	Xynas	Constantinos	ABE	xynas@abe.gr
17	Ziougou	Chrysovalantou	CERTH	ziougou@cperi.certh.gr

REVIEWERS LIST

List of Reviewers (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Arena	Damiano	EPFL	damiano.arena@epfl.ch
2	Morello	Michele	ISMB	morello@ismb.it

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Explanation or definition
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
API	Application programming interface
AR	Augmented reality
BSC	Business Scenario
CAD	Computer aided design
CRUD	In computer programming, create, read, update and delete are the four basic functions of persistent storage
DCC	Digital Content Creation
DFD	Data flow diagram, a diagramming methodology to specify processes
DG RTD	European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
DMAIC	Acronym for Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve and Control. Refers to a data-driven improvement cycle used for improving, optimizing and stabilizing business processes and designs.
DOW	The Description of Work, a formal SatisFactory project document
EC	European Commission
ECOGRAI	A method to design and to implement Performance Indicator Systems (PIS) for industrial organizations.
EFQM	European Foundation for Quality Management
EOP	Emergency Operating Procedures
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020 is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever, with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020)
HMD	Head Mounted Display
ICT	Information and communication technology
KPI	Key performance Indicator

HMI	Human Machine Interface
JDK	Java Development Kit
LMS	Learning Management Systems
M20	SatisFactory project Milestone at Month 20
M30	SatisFactory project Milestone at Month 30
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport is a lightweight messaging protocol for small sensors and mobile devices, optimized for high-latency or unreliable networks
OM	Ontology Manager
OP	Operating Procedures
PIS	Performance Indicator System
RGBD	Red, Green, Blue, Depth. Imaging technology providing multi spectral images where the three optical bands: R, G, B, are coupled with a distance (time of flight) reading
SCM	Supply chain management
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLIC	Simple Linear Iterative Clustering
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TCT	Training Creation tool
TEP	Training and educational platform
TPM	Total Productive Maintenance
TPT	Training Presentation tool
TS	Training system
TM	Talent management
UC	Use Case
U.N.	United Nations
VR	Virtual reality

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020). It describes the intended achievement of the T2.5 Task, i.e. the On the Job Training and Educational Platform, a set of tools developed to implement new training models and interfaces using augmented reality and 3D model animations according to the guidelines defined by a set of scenarios previously identified. The A.R. platform designed and developed in the task T4.3 is a fundamental component of the On the Job Training and Educational Platform; this means that, even if the On the Job Training and Educational Platform has its own technologies and software modules, the description provided within the scope of this deliverable must be intended as additional to the description provided in the D4.3.2 [REF21] The latter should be ideally kept open as reference to provide insight into the platform and the technology context where the more process oriented statements about the current deliverable must be placed.

In this document, after the introduction, the user needs driving the achievements of the T2.5 tasks are discussed in short, distinguishing between manufacturing and maintenance procedures, in order to help in understanding the overall motivations of the task. Second, a state of the art analysis about the training in manufacturing environments is performed, taking in account the innovation brought to this field by the augmented reality and the virtual reality technologies, being the A.R. platform designed and delivered by the T4.3 task the key tool adopted by T2.5 to build the Training Platform. These sections have to be put in relationship with the specific requirements of the DOW, stating: "On the basis of tasks T1.1 and T1.3, specific training needs will be identified and used in combination with a group of case scenarios in order to design novel training models and interfaces for the widening of employees knowledge and skills through the use of Augmented Reality technologies."

The key section that follows the state of the art analysis depicts the specific scenarios related to the "in-the-Job training", i.e. a one-on-one training located at the job site, where someone who knows how to do a task shows to another person, less acquainted with the job, how to perform it. It is a model of training consisting of the several distinguishing features. Their implementation will be a paramount achievement of the T2.5 task, so the scenario involved is described in details.

In the two following sections, the two major platform components: the A.R. Training Tools and the Training Data Analysis Tool are described. Their interplay is especially important because the log / audit data flow from the A.R. Training Tools could be transformed, by means of the Training Data Analysis Tool, in KPIs. Those KPIs could be used as feedback by a specific professional in order to finely tune the training data session, improve continuously the effectiveness of the training provided.

The annexes that could be found at the end of the document contain essential technical specifications about the log data, listing what data are logged by the Training Platform, what is the format of the log data. Examples of log data are provided.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE

As stressed in the executive summary, the Training Platform inherits the overall design and its fundamental features from the A.R. In-Factory Platform, which is, in its turn, the outcome of the T4.3 task aimed to specify, then implement, a set of multiplatform tools able to support assembly and maintenance operations using augmented reality and 3D model animations. The main distinction between the achievements of T4.3 and T2.5 could be stated in the very same terms reported in the introduction of the D4.3.2 [REF21] T4.3 deals mainly with the implementation of a platform, while T2.5 deals with the implementation of a specific application of that platform. A major factor proving that the task deals mainly with a platform application is the fact that the effort to be delivered by ABE, the partner bringing to the task the body of knowledge about the training processes, is of the same order of magnitude of the joined effort in charge of the same partners that are the technology providers involved in T4.3, namely REGOLA together with CERTH, aiming to implement all the ancillary tools enabling the platform to perform its mission as a true, efficient and innovative training application.

The Training Platform is composed by three fundamental components:

1. **The Training Creation tool**, a desktop application to be used to design then implement the Training Operative Procedures.
2. **The Training Presentation tool**, a multiplatform application where the Training Operative Procedures are served and executed to perform training sessions.
3. **The Training Data Analytics tool**, the application intended to provide valuable insight into the training sessions. This is achieved by transforming the log data provided by the Presentation tool inner working in firmly established KPIs, and visualizing these KPIs in a way that is suitable to get a better understanding of the overall process to be used to improve the training operating procedures driving the training sessions. These KPIs are further processed to provide higher level of knowledge by means of the Ontology Manager (OM). This will follow the indications and rules defined by ABE thanks to its experience in the training delivered in the manufacturing field, and then, coded by EPFL, which is the SatisFactory partner having the skills required to formalize and implement such mechanism in the SatisFactory knowledge base.

One of the tools that will add to the A.R. platform significant capabilities, specific to the Training Platform, has the important responsibility to provide bi-directional communications among the platforms involved in training sessions. In facts, in a typical training scenario, a trainer and one or many trainees must be able to communicate among them to share a training session in which the trainee must give evidence to the trainer of how well he/she is performing and, in its turn, the trainer must be able to provide rich feedback to the trainee. The specific tool to be developed to support those capabilities will be the bi-directional communication plugin. This tool must not be confused with the View Channel, a general A.R. platform plugin that will be available in the A.R. platform and that is intended as a one-way general communication service that could be used by any SatisFactory module to send prioritized, media rich dispatches to the Presentation tools

running in the factory. It will support the user in sending single direction, multi-media, prioritized dispatches bringing messages to the A.R. platform, namely in the context of a training session.

As said before, a significant role in this task is played by Atlantis Engineering (ABE) that, according to the DOW, will make available its specific skills in training factory's personnel to perform several types of manufacturing procedures. In facts, one objective for the T2.5 task is to provide the body of knowledge required to design ways to extract meaningful log data from the A.R. platform inner workings, transforming that audit data in KPIs, i.e. information relevant to the training sessions. That information could be used in order to assess how well the trainees have performed in their training session and how well the Training Platform performs in supporting trainers, trainee, training experts, and procedure engineers when serving Training Operating Procedures. Looking at the overall training process, a key factor is that the KPIs could be used as feedback to the training procedures design phase, to finely tune them, in order to better fit the needs that, at the end of the day, should result in an overall, verifiable improvement of the trainee skills and in his/her increased self-confidence about how well he/she is performing the job. This is the important fact that must be highlighted: all the training sessions are intended to provide rich information that, according to the more general aims of the Satisfactory project, must be put at the service of the workers improving how much they are comfortable with their duties. To do so, the whole Training Platform must help in shaping a specific professional profile having its own, distinctive skills: the training procedure designer, i.e. that professional profile to which, eventually, all the information provided by the training sessions are fed. In this aspect the KPI, the training data visualization and the processing performed on them by means of an Ontology Manager, should be intended as a support to the human using the Creation Tool in order to continuously improve the training operating procedures.

The training areas to be addressed have been already defined within WP1, the work package led by COMAU that is in charge of performing domain analysis and requirements engineering. Typical needs to be addressed are: machinery monitoring, critical issues on certain manufacturing operations, maintenance procedures including predictive maintenance, condition based and reactive maintenance as well as best practices for some daily and periodic operations in the shop floor. As in the D4.3, the deliverable is released stepwise in two phases: M20 and M30. In the first, basic version, some training capabilities will be added to the A.R. platform for Satisfactory Operations; in the second step the full On the Job Training and Educational Platform will be implemented and released.

2.2 REQUIREMENTS

The specific requirements driving the On the Job Training and Educational Platform design and implementation are a subset of the more general requirements listed in the deliverable D1.1.1 titled: "User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines". It is a document that is a formal deliverable of the T1.1 task of the Satisfactory project. In the following table we include a selection of the requirements that are strictly related to the AR Training platform and, for this reason, have been not mentioned in the D4.3.2 [REF21] . Please, refer to the D4.3.2 [REF21] for a list of the requirements related to the A.R. in-Factory platform; further, refer to D1.1.1 for the whole requirement set and for an explanation of the widely known methodologies adopted for their definition.

Comment [TR1]: D4.3.2? or better, D4.3?

Comment [AS2]:

Key	Summary	Priority	Description	Fit Criterion
SAFA-52	Multimedia training procedures	Blocker	Video or audio recorded procedures could be available for new operators and technicians	There are several training procedures can be performed through multimedia platform
SAFA-47	Platform training	Minor	The introduction of new terminals could lead to the introduction of new training in order to let the people work with these new devices	A manual to use the platform is available
SAFA-37	Multimedia training procedures	Blocker	IT architecture provides an innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures and sessions	At least 1 training procedure can be performed through multimedia platform

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3. TRAINING PROCEDURES ADDRESSED. RELATIONSHIPS TO T1.3

3.1 SPECIFIC USER NEEDS: THE CURRENT ISSUES

The main issues in the training activities currently carried out are related to the huge amount of specific, additional paperwork required by them. Further, there is a significant need for additional resources “needed to train the trainees”. The adoption of the innovative training platform proposed by the SatisFactory project fully addresses these issues in full, providing a Training Platform always available and always up-to-date, being fed by data retrieved from a centralized server embodied in a self-contained, versioned, media-rich bundle. Moreover, being the training Presentation tool used to serve the training procedures a multiplatform application, remote support can be provided by the means of augmented reality glasses. This could allow the involvement as trainers of employees that are possibly busy in other assembly operations (or maintenance, in case that a maintenance scenario is currently addressed).

3.2 USERS / ACTORS: CASE SCENARIOS

In COMAU business scenarios a professional training is expected to be applied to two different categories of workers:

1. The “blue collars”, i.e. the operators that physically need training. Reasons for the training could be the following:
 - 1.1. They are new to the job. They are new workers joining the company; they could be temporary workers or permanent workers. These persons need to learn the procedures required to assemble the COMAU products, and within the SATISFACTORY project perimeter of the robot sub-groups. Today this training is performed placing the new workers side by side with experienced operators that transfer to them their knowledge with a training on the job, as well as providing documents that describe step by step the assembly operations for each specific robot sub-group.
 - 1.2. Some updates are required in the existing procedures. Workers already in the company may require training because of procedures change or updates, or because of the introduction of new products. Typically, these updates are communicated to operators giving them printed procedures to be followed step by step and cycle after cycle, until they are learned and the print is not needed anymore.
2. The Technical Leaders, as well as the Design & Ergonomic Engineers, that are in charge of the design of the workplaces and the formalization of the Standard Operating Procedures to be used during training and operation.

The training procedures applied in COMAU now are based on the standard operating procedures, thus the documents used for training are exactly the same that are used for normal operations.

3.2.1 Manufacturing Operations

The first Business Scenario (BSC-1.1) in COMAU use-cases is related with the operations and procedures that are performed to assemble a robot arm at the shop floor, including the wiring and its cabinet configuration. This assembly process is currently performed in a completely manual way and it is based on specific steps, being each of them performed in a specific assembly workplace. During the week, according to workload and operator availability, the workers could move in the different assembly stations, thus performing different operations. The SatisFactory Project aims to develop in this environment a sensor rich workplace coupled with user interfaces that could run both on a fixed (A.R. HMI) or mobile (A.R. Glasses) terminal. This system will continuously guide the operator providing contextual information in the assembly operations and monitoring the steps performed for correctness. The scenario applies both to training and operation phases.

3.2.2 Maintenance Procedures

The second Business Scenario deals with activities supporting the operations that take place at the Body Assembly COMAU customer's shop floor. Maintenance is an important aspect in the lifecycle of a production system. In order to ensure proper working conditions, periodic check activities must be performed and some components must be replaced. COMAU does not perform maintenance operations directly, but provides to its customer specific procedures describing the main maintenance operations to be performed and their schedule. Sometimes, in case of critical faults, COMAU engineers are required to interface with customer's maintenance staff in order to fix them. The Application Scenario deals with both the training and the operation phases is: "BSC-2.1 Remote Maintenance at manufacturing production lines". In this scenario the maintenance staff, equipped with A.R. glasses and/or tablets, will receive remote support from the colleagues in the office (a "virtual remote control room") that will help in solving issues that are particularly critical, reducing significantly the MTTR of the automatic machines.

4. TRAINING: STATE OF THE ART ANALYSIS

In this section the current status of the training methods used for training especially in industrial and corporate environments is reported. The progress on, and the added value from the deployment of A.R. and/or V.R. technologies is also evaluated.

4.1 RELATIONSHIPS WITH THE T1.2

4.1.1 Groups of workers that are using Training and Educational platform

The Training and Education platform is mostly dedicated to novices and/or trainee workers in order to show to them various procedures to be performed in the shop floor. Furthermore, even experienced workers can be assisted by means of the platform when a difficult or a completely new procedure must currently be carried out in the shop floor. The following list shows, for each shop floor, the groups of workers who can be involved in the training operations and that will possibly benefit from the training (or the on the job training) at the three shop floors involved in the project.

COMAU:

COMAU's actors that are involved at Satisfactory project belong to three categories (Technical Leader, Process operator, Design and Ergonomic engineer). This categorization is based on their role and on the procedures that they usually perform. Two of these categories can greatly benefit from the educational and training activities. More specifically:

- **Process operator.** According to the task to be carried out, specialized operations have to be performed by skilled operators.
- **Design and ergonomic engineer.** They are involved mainly with: the design of layout of machines; the mechanical design; the electrical/software/hydraulic design; the ergonomics and safety issues.

The third group is the Technical Leader that could use ad hoc training sessions when he or she starts working at the specific environment as a trainee or novice.

SUNLIGHT:

In both lines that are involved in the SATISFACTORY project, staff with different responsibilities are involved. They are grouped into the following categories:

1. Plant manager;
2. Production planner;
3. Production supervisors;
4. Shop floor leaders and workers (expert, novice).

Also a technical and maintenance team (technicians, technical manager) is kept in standby to react, should unplanned incidents occur. The categories that can benefit from the educational and training activities are:

1. **Technicians.** They are responsible for handling the training and the development needs of new hires and for implementing preventive maintenance programs.
2. **Foreman.** Coordinates daily production floor activities and delegate assignments to production personnel monitoring employee's work performances relative to expectations and maintaining material / workflow through the facility
3. **Workers.** Involved with measuring, grading and feeding batches of raw materials into production machinery. They operate production line equipment and assemble goods in a production line.

The other groups (Maintenance Manager, Production supervisor and Production Plant manager) could use ad hoc training sessions when a specific need arises.

CERTH/CPERI:

At CERTH/CPERI shop floor there are two main categories of actors; one related to the process operations and the other to the maintenance activities, whereas both are coordinated and supervised by the "Floor Manager". Also the maintenance team is broken into three categories of groups according to the area of expertise, namely the mechanical-process, the electrical, and the automation related group. The categories that can benefit from the educational and training activities are:

1. **Process technician.** Supports and maintains pilot plants operation and is involved in new constructions and revamps.
2. **Electrical technician.** Responsible for maintaining schematics, electrical cabinets, is involved in new constructions and revamps.
3. **Automation technician.** Responsible for maintaining automation and ICT infrastructures and is involved in new constructions and revamps.
4. **Process operator.** Performs Daily operations at the pilot plants.

The groups that have been identified as candidate to use the On the Job Training and Educational Platform can benefit not only of the new training procedures, when they are available, but also of the help received in remembering procedures that they have not performed for a significant period of time. More details about the characteristics and aspects of the actors can be found at deliverable "D1.2 - Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description".

Comment [TR3]: As before

4.1.3 Business Scenarios where Training and Education platform is addressed

The Business Scenarios that have been created have been originated from the three end users (COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH) of Satisfactory and each one targets different facets of the operations and activities that take place at the shop floor with respect to the worker's involvement and collaboration. Some of these BSCs are using the Training and Education platform in order to provide some tools able to improve how daily actions are performed at the shop floors by the workers involved. Moreover, the business scenarios are developed taking in account the needs and requirements of the workers. These requirements, as said in the introduction of this document,

are described in details in the deliverable D1.1 “User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines”.

At the first shop floor, at COMAU premises, the platform is used in:

1. BSC-1.1 - Manual assembly operations with focus on Robot Wrist assembly and
2. BSC-1.2 - Automated assembly operations with focus on Welding Gun assembly

At the second shop floor, at SUNLIGHT premises, the Training and Educational platform is used in:

3. BSC-4.3 - Training platform for production process motive power batteries assembly line.

At the third shop floor, at CERTH premises, the platform is used in:

4. BSC-5.2 - Startup procedures for pilot plants

All the above BSCs involve mostly novice and/or trainee workers; experienced workers could also be involved and assisted by means of the platform as well. More details about actors, UCs and BSCs can be found in Deliverable “D1.2 - Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description”.

4.2 INDUSTRIAL / CORPORATE / PROFESSIONAL TRAINING: THE STATE OF THE ART

There may be a longer or shorter road until Industry 4.0 becomes the prevailing reality in the European manufacturing scenario, but the framework is gradually changing and the on-the-job training in a corporate and/or industrial environment is on the same path. The importance of corporate training is associated with steady global changes, technological breakthroughs, continuity over time and indicators of financial and business performance that make organizational environments increasingly competitive. A major milestone for a company, in corporate level, would include the efficient and cost effective training of employees, under the condition that business and human rights are not influenced (U.N. Guiding Principles, 2011). Eventually, this could create added value to the company, regardless of overall market conditions, since knowledge, skills and abilities will be successfully developed to company personnel.

In the near future to live, some level of digital skills will be needed to work in 90% of the jobs. This is why in March 2013 the European Commission launched the **Grand Coalition for Digital Jobs**; the largest, multi-stakeholder collaborative effort in Europe, aimed to offer more ICT training co-designed with the industry; to implement job placement programmes; to provide more digitally aligned degrees and curricula at all levels and types of training and education. More information about this could be found in the reference: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/grand-coalition-digital-jobs>.

It is noted that it is possible to classify the ways that professional training is provided, capitalising also on the experience of the Satisfactory partners, as well as to examine the relative state of the art, the existing tools and formats of best practices.

4.2.1 “Traditional” training methods

In the context of this deliverable, with the term “traditional” training we refer to methods demanding actual physical presence simultaneously with the trainer. In essence, they are off-the-job training models, but they are usually the most common and prevailing method. Even in this case, four options can be discerned.

Figure 1 Instructor lead training

Comment [TR4]: The figure caption should be updated (e.g. Figure 1 to Figure 1)

1) Instructor-Lead Training

In the case shown in Figure 1, there is an instructor, the teacher, coming from inside or outside of the company. It takes place in some kind of classroom or conference room using overhead projectors, presentations, videos, and storytelling. It can be as fun and as interactive as the instructor wants, motivating employees to compare results and share ideas (Sliver, 2015). The classroom training is commonly used for beginning levels (Pallo, 2012).

2) Interactive training in smaller groups

This training concept, shown in Figure 2, capitalises on techniques to involve groups of employees, usually less than 10, with tools coming from Quality Assurance, TPM, EFQM and the like. Brainstorming, quizzes, case studies, questions and answers, role playing, DMAIC etc. can be used. This approach still involves a leading instructor or guru, or at least a moderator to keep the employees engaged. The active involvement in the form of group discussions allows for knowledge sharing, open communication among the trainees and with the trainer and exchange of ideas. Demonstration or case studies can be used to trigger rigorous discussions. The key in this case is that the participants interact freely, not rejecting, but evaluating all ideas. The instructor still needs to showcase the steps being taught or the main processes.

Figure 2 Interactive training

Comment [TR5]: The figure caption should be updated (e.g. Figure 2 to Figure 2)

3) Coaching

Coaching involves a mentor, a coach and a small group, usually from 1 to 5 people. It is the most focused and customised type of traditional training, which allows to quickly identify strong and weak areas. It is also the way traditionally training is being done in an industrial environment, where there is a supervisor that assumes the role of the instructor, usually towards new employees. (<http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/employees/training-methods-on-job-training-and-off-the-job-training-methods/5421/>)

4) Vestibule training

Vestibule Training is the intermediate between off-the-job and on-the-job, because the employees are trained using a prototype or in a simulated environment. The training duration spans from a few days to a few weeks. Generally speaking, with this method an attempt is made to create working conditions similar to the workshop conditions that the specific workers will need to face in their actual job. It can also serve as a precursor of the on-the job training.

(<http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/employees/training-methods-on-job-training-and-off-the-job-training-methods/5421/>)

4.2.2 E-learning

E-learning is becoming a viable and attractive alternative to training, directed towards people's motivations and needs, by permitting classes attendance anywhere, anytime, in a more informal way (Anderson, 2015). It emerged as a result of the combination of technology with human interaction. This trend has been translated into the availability of a variety of e-learning platforms, Learning Management Systems (LMS) and Talent Management (TM) Systems. An analysis in 2014 has shown that for the e-learning market, the five-year compound annual growth rate is estimated at around 7.6%, hence worldwide revenues could reach \$51.5 billion by 2016. For the Western Europe the market value was estimated to reach \$8.1 billion in 2016 with an estimated annual growth rate of 5.8% in 2013-16 (Docebo, 2014). On the other hand, this type has to cope with the drawback of reduced interest or engagement of the trainees.

A more recent study report on Global E-learning Market expects its growth rate at CAGR to be 17.81% within 2016-2020 (Technavio, January 2016). The in-depth market analysis was implemented with inputs from industry experts and key vendors (namely Adobe, Blackboard, Oracle and SAP), as well as with the consideration of prominent vendors.

In the context of this deliverable, two subcategories/types can be considered:

1. Training using existing e-learning platforms/talent management solutions and content
2. Training using dedicated and custom made online courses for a specific company.

A. Training using existing e-learning platforms/talent management solutions and content

When we refer to the category A, we consider the solution that is usually employed for training on soft skills and on general competences. It is also plausible to say that in this case it is possible to use already available content freely, for example in the form of MOOCs, using MOODLE or in a pay-per-use platform. This method has not many supporters when it comes to training in industrial manufacturing, as it is considered too time consuming to look for and locate the best suitable solution for each company. Moreover, security and ethical restrictions hinder the broad adoption of type A e-learning.

B. Training using dedicated and custom made online courses for a specific company

When we refer to the category B, we consider solutions that can be used for training both on soft and on hard skills. Multiple solutions are available here too, mainly because this type is, or at least feels, more customised to the end users in hand. The training can be offered via an online platform

or an application. It can be in a form of a presentation with more or less interactive features or of a virtual classroom or of a webinar.

Online courses can promote professional development and also networking with other trainers, including information platform, which ensures access to day-to-day training tips in form of virtual seminars and sessions (CEDEFOP, 2010). Statistical data reveal that this type of corporate training accounts for 20% and 29% for small and larger (medium and large) enterprises, respectively. A report on Training industry (Trainmag, 2014) revealed that the following results are expected, when the type of online courses was selected as a methodology for corporate training:

1. flexibility and convenience;
2. constant availability of technical support, whenever required;
3. equal results as for the effectiveness of the information provided.

It is important to note that in the case of virtual classrooms, the non-physical presence, the absence of proximity to the instructor and the anonymity feeling of the trainees can cause communication issues, especially since a considerable amount of participants may not be familiar with e-learning. Hence, it is indispensable to set rules in the beginning of such an effort in terms of how to treat everyone in this context, what is allowed or not, how and when to pose questions etc. This is a key when the training is on Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), especially in industrial manufacturing.

In terms of market penetration, this solution is more popular for large, high-end and ICT oriented companies, where an acceptable ROI can be attained and where the management is more inclined to invest in uniform and sometimes simultaneous training. Examples are the Learning@Work from SABA, used by leaders in automotive, manufacturing, aviation, healthcare and more. Also, TalentLMS, LearnUpon, Paradiso, Litmos and WalkMe offer interesting products, popular for enterprise training.

4.2.3 Training using novel tools such as Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR).

In corporate venues, A.R. corresponds to a collaborative, skill-learning, explainable, and guidable tool for workers, managers, and customers. In the field of industrial maintenance (example provided in figure 3) A.R. is considered a very practical assistance for employees of highly demanding technical work, thus achieving great efficiency and effectiveness (Lee, 2012). Also, as an On-the-Job training method, A.R. offers the **advantages** of being:

1. informal,
2. effective because it is learning by experience,
3. directly in the context of the job,
4. free from artificial classroom situations,
5. highly motivating to trainees.

(<http://www.whatishumanresource.com/on-the-job-methods>)

Figure 3 Augmented reality based training

The **disadvantages** are mostly related with the use of specific devices and apparatuses to augment a worker's natural view with text, labels, arrows, and animated sequences designed to facilitate task comprehension, location, and execution. Moreover, issues related to the effect on the workers' health are still being addressed, trying to figure out a way to find optimal usage time and reduction of dizziness, motion sickness, headaches. Programming physics, costs, under development and graphics are also other factors limiting the growth of the global augmented reality and virtual reality market (Persistence, 2016). Additionally, privacy issues and image latency may also inhibit the wide application of this type of corporate training.

Regarding the **opportunities** in the manufacturing field, it should be noted that currently its market share is considered comparatively low. On the other hand, the projections are highly challenging. A recently published report by Goldman Sachs assumes a revenue of 1.5 billion \$ for the year 2020, with SatisFactory projections of tripling it in the year 2025. The revenues are expected to stem from subscription fees of a continuously-expanding basis of users (Goldman Sachs, 2016).

From what has been discussed until now it can be deduced that A.R. and V.R. are a more or less combined growing market where the big players of industrial manufacturing and maintenance don't want to be left behind. The most advanced companies, usually multinationals, estimate that A.R./V.R. will be a significant game changer and they want to have first a view of that world, to be the early adopters and rule makers. A lot of issues still remain to be solved, such as health and safety and the relative legislation. Moreover, CEOs need to be convinced on the ROI of engaging an endeavour to introduce such systems in their companies. At this point it should be noted that, depending on the specific application case, one needs to **select between A.R. or V.R.**, assessing which of them may be more or less suitable for, or at least acceptable by, the workers, supervisor and management. For example, for short messages and simple instructions, A.R. has been reported by stakeholders as more suitable. On the other hand, the presentation of more complex models or procedures may be better accepted using V.R., where the worker is immersed in the

task for a short period of time and there are no issues with relative movement to the objects demonstrated in A.R. models. However, for larger periods of time during the work day, V.R. may be an unwanted solution, because it can make the workers feel too detached from the reality or even make them more prone to accidents, since they are not in touch much with the real world. Consequently, this choice depends upon the specific application, the company and the business field or operation that wants to make use of these novel technologies, together with the developers/vendors/mentors promoting that technology.

There are two other factors that need also to be considered; namely, cost and scalability.

With regards to **cost**, A.R. and V.R. usage is associated first of all with equipment cost, i.e. A.R. and V.R. glasses. Then, there is the cost of the used platform and/or application enabling the use of the A.R./V.R. features. Corporate solutions are getting less inclined to spend over time and the entrance of multiple players in the worldwide market fosters competition and lowers prices. Mass solutions offering, of courses having less possibilities than an actual A.R./V.R. headset, are becoming available (such as Google Cardbox, SMARTvr and more), making it at least simpler to test these technologies with no need for significant investments.

To this end, **scalability** or even replicability become possible and plausible opportunities for A.R. and V.R. developers and vendors. It is the general feeling of the end users that A.R. and V.R. involves too much customisation and effort into generating the exact models for a specific company or operation. This notion can be turned around with solutions that automate steps or even the complete procedure. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, there is already a number of e-learning platforms that are looking to interface with A.R. or V.R. systems, or even to offer online A.R./V.R. training. So, at least some partial interoperability can be foreseen in the immediate future.

4.2.4 Training model selection

Selecting the appropriate training model each time depends on: the scope, the resources, the company culture, the target group, the result sought and more. It is worth mentioning that in some cases there is a cultural bias in favour or against certain training models and that not all levels and subjects of training require the same training model. However, it is commonly accepted that a company can reduce quality losses by increasing knowledge of their workers (Newbegin, 2016). Hence, before moving forward with one method or the other, it is advised to clearly analyse the scope of the training, associating it with measurable and tangible results that need to be both qualitative and quantitative. The evaluation methodology adopted within the SatisFactory project in D5.2 can be a helpful start as it takes into account different objectives and criteria, as well as two different points of view; the workers and the decision-makers. Both stakeholder groups need to agree and elements of the ECOGRAI methodology could be considered for application here too (Lobna, 2013).

Regarding the use of novel technologies in training, it has been proved that assembly applications can benefit substantially from the improved memorization attainable via A.R. which can shorten the training time of new employees (Ke, 2005). Enhancement of long-term memory is also a strong positive factor in the understanding and retention of assembly or repair sequences, procedures and other information. Aiming towards a holistic approach where education and orientation correspond to the cornerstone of training methodologies, the use of V.R. and A.R. tools is

expected not only to achieve great efficiency and effectiveness, regarding company requirements, but also to assure safety, accuracy and convenience for employees.

The concept for any A.R. platform is to address a wide user base, multiple stakeholders and international clients. Issues to be considered are related to different expectations, models, but also cultural differences. For example, gestures to be demonstrated with a 3D model via the A.R. toolkit should not be considered offensive in the specific culture/country where the training takes place. Also, in case of verbal instructions presented, the wording and pronunciation should be also treated with caution.

For all those reasons, a combination of different training models tuned according to company-specific factors is appropriate. In this mix, the use of novel technologies needs to be included; as the company and the involved personnel grow and mature, a shift from the traditional training methods to e-learning and to A.R./V.R. is expected.

5. ON THE JOB TRAINING

With the current expansion of the global economy and the fast-changing evolution of the technology and the innovation that it produces, factories are facing a constant need for improved employee learning and training methods development. As knowledge increasingly becomes a key factor for productivity, it is steadily becoming a driving force for competitive success. On-the-job training, refers to a one-on-one training located at the job site, where someone who knows how to do a task shows to another person, less acquainted with the job, how to perform it. In the scope of Industry 4.0, on-the-job training becomes a key way to ensure the adoption of new processes, skills and methodologies by the workforce to support the need for flexible and adaptable production requirements as well as to provide fast and effective training to new workers. The introduction of novel technologies inside the smart factories of the future, adds new ways to envision such a training methodology that support both supervised and unsupervised sessions, direct feedback and detailed analytics on worker performances as well as multi-modal training material.

Within the scope of SatisFactory, on-the-job training is a model of training, consisting of the following features:

1. Standard Operating Procedure capture and encoding, translating it into step-by-step sequences to be performed in training sessions.
2. Multi-modal training material preparation, supporting the above stepwise training scheme.
3. Marker-based and markerless A.R. as well as V.R. interfaces directly applied and brought, through mobile and desktop systems, on the shop floor.
4. Bi-directional communication facilities to enable trainee/supervisor exchange of information during training.
5. Data Logging, Gesture Recognition and Data Analytics to evaluate trainee performance.
6. Integration with the Collaboration Platform and gamification elements to boost trainee engagement.

The application of each of the above features in each specific use case depends on several factors including feasibility of deployment, user needs, safety regulations and usability concerns.

For example, in all three pilot sites (COMAU, Sunlight and CPERI), workers can only use handheld mobile devices when they are not actually operating machinery, performing assembly operations or handling any material, because most, if not all, operating procedures on the shop-floor require the use of both hands and uninterrupted attention to the work to be currently done. Thus, any training scenario involving on-the-job training with a mobile device other than a head mounted display (which itself has several limitations) must be implemented in one of two ways. The first way involves only watching on the mobile device the augmented reality presentation of the training steps without actually performing the operation steps during the training session. The second way involves first watching the training material and then releasing the mobile device to perform the action using both hands. Both cases limit the applicability of certain features, one of most important of them being the evaluation of trainee performance. In particular, there is no usable way to use the mobile device's camera and sensors as means to evaluate trainee performance by recording data and performing gesture recognition using them while the trainee performs the action, since most operations require both hands available by the trainee. The restrictions described dictate the

need to use desktop devices in certain cases in combination with static installations of RGB and depth cameras to support both the markerless object detection and registration as well as the gesture recognition.

For the reasons stated above we describe in the following figures the different setups explored to provide as many of the proposed functionalities for on-the-job training as possible given the requirements in each pilot site.

5.1 ON THE JOB TRAINING: SETUP #1

Figure 4 Setup 1, handheld device/No verification of trainee operations

The setup described in the figure 4, outlines the scenario where:

1. the trainee performs on-the-job training via a handheld device (namely a tablet);
2. the A.R. Presentation tool performs marker-based object registration using the on-board RGB camera of the tablet and information is presented on top of the video captured by the camera on the tablet screen.

This setup has the advantage that it only requires a single device to be used by the trainee during a training session, where all training information in multiple formats can be accessed. However, it also comes with several restrictions.

First of all, as we mentioned already, however convenient the use of tablet computers may be, on the shop floor it is not always possible to perform the activities described in the training sessions and hold the tablet at the same time. This means that in this setup, validation of the trainee performance on each step of the procedure, based on gesture recognition, object recognition and operation semantics, are not performed and trainee evaluation is based on the metrics recorded by the Training Platform alone referenced in Section 6.1.1. Some of those metrics can be influenced by shop floor data that are available to the platform that are relevant to the training tasks under evaluation, as long as this data (e.g. equipment states and measurements) are included as part of the training scenario when it is created.

Second, the use of markers for A.R. object registration is not always possible due to the form of the operation. A.R. markers need to be placed in specific positions relative to the actual installations or objects for which they will provide registration for virtual media. There are several situations where this is not feasible. For example, in the Sunlight factory battery assembly training scenario of BSC4.2, the assembly parts are never in an exact location and therefore there are no suitable positions for the placement of markers. Therefore, setup 1 cannot be applied in this case. However, the setup above can be used in the CPERI BSC 5.2 training scenario, since the location, as well as most of the instruments, equipment and tools, are on a fixed installation where several candidate locations for marker placement are available. In any case, the trainee evaluation is carried out at the end of the training session, while bidirectional communication between trainee and training supervisor can be carried out at any time during the session.

5.2 ON THE JOB TRAINING: SETUP #2

Figure 5 Desktop device, verification of trainee operations

The second setup, shown in the figure 5, uses a desktop computer solution which in turn provides the ability to use external cameras to support Markerless A.R. as well as Object and Gesture Recognition. Since the installation of such a setup requires a static placement of both the interaction devices and the display, it is better suited for training scenarios, where the operations are carried out in a specific environment, where the trainee can both perform the operation as well as watch the training material on the screen. Such an environment is met in the COMAU shop floor, where manual assembly operations are carried out in static work surfaces where both the screen and cameras of the desktop systems can be mounted both out of the way of the employees but at the same time offer ample viewing coverage.

In this setup, it is possible to combine both shop floor data (if they are available via sensors) as well as semantic gesture recognition, to support stepwise verification of trainee performance. For example, in an assembly scenario, with such a setup it is possible for the trainee to first watch the step being virtually performed on the screen and then perform the step, in order to proceed with the training scenario. The availability of gesture and object recognition modules, in combination with the shop floor data can determine the correct or false performance of each step in the process automatically without supervisor interference and provide additional evaluation metrics for each trainee.

5.3 ON THE JOB TRAINING: SETUP #3

Figure 6 Setup 3, Mobile device: partial verification of some trainee operations through custom tools

There are several situations where neither the first nor the second setup can meet the requirements of a training scenario. One such case, is the training scenario for battery assembly training in Sunlight portrayed in figure 6. The assembly line in the Sunlight shop-floor does not deal with a set of operations carried out over the same component, since the types of batteries being built are dependent on each order. Furthermore, the assembly is not performed over a work surface but on an open assembly space over different areas for each 4-5 steps of the procedure and the number of different types of batteries built and their variations are in the hundreds. A snapshot showing the environment of one of the assembly areas is demonstrated in figure 6. We can see there, at least two types of battery boxes being worked on at different stages of assembly, which means that depending on the type of battery and the placement of the battery box by the forklift in each area where a different stage of the assembly is carried out, the A.R. material and mostly, the relevant data to support verification of assembly operations vary greatly. It is therefore very hard to follow the methodology of the second setup (which relies in the training of object models for recognition and registration).

In this case, we must use a custom markerless solution as well as a custom verification module, in order to support A.R. presentations and verification of correct performance of operations.

Figure 7 Assembly Environment in Sunlight

The solutions we have come up with in this setup are described in detail in section 5.2.5, while the A.R. algorithms developed to implement these solutions are described in D4.3.2 [REF21]

5.4 ON THE JOB TRAINING: SETUP #4

Figure 8 Setup 4: Handheld/Desktop in combination with HMD

The last setup we explored, depicted in figure 8, makes use of the GlassUP see-through HMD in combination with either a handheld or desktop device configuration. In this setup, the HMD acts as a secondary screen that overlays text and images in the field of view of the trainee, aiding in the performance of each step of the training session, while the main interface into the scenario is handled by either a handheld or desktop device as in setups 2 and 3. The existence of an RGB camera integrated with the HMD provides the capability to use it as an external camera source for certain scenarios either for marker-based or markerless AR. However, due to the limited processing power afforded by the HMD, the combination of video + 3D data in the HMD display is not feasible, hence the need for another visualization device with the HMD acting as a secondary training information screen.

6. PLATFORM COMPONENTS: THE AR TRAINING TOOLS

6.1 AR CREATION TOOL CUSTOMIZED FOR TRAINING

This chapter describes the specific training and education features introduced in the Creation Tool. By means of this customization, it is possible to distinguish the Training Creation Tool (TCT) from the more general Creation Tool as introduced in D4.3.2 [REF21]. The TCT is based on and uses many of the features of the Creation Tool, expanding both the set of data that can be handled and the exposed functionality.

6.1.1 Creation of a training procedure

The Training Creation Tool gives the possibility to create a training procedure (TP) in the following ways:

1. From scratch.
2. From an existing operating procedure.
3. From a subtree of an already existing operating procedure.

The most interesting aspect of a Training Procedure is that, within it, it is possible to force a specific, predefined value from the sensors available in the shop-floor. This allows to have the same conditions exposed to the trainees performing the Training Procedure, so that it becomes possible to assess their work in an objective manner. Further, by means of this capability it becomes possible to expose the worker to specific, predefined conditions in order to assess their reaction to specific occurrences. This feature is based on the definition of the **Conditional Relationship**.

6.1.2 Defining the conditions

In the **Conditional Relationship**, via a Condition Editor, it is possible to get conditional procedure execution by means of branching of the procedure. This branching is achieved inserting, by means of the Creation Tool, conditions that are evaluated at runtime by the A.R. OP Presentation Tool performing actual sensor reading according to the choices made in the procedure editing. In the Training Creation tool, it is possible to force the values of these sensors, at will of the trainer, by inserting plausible values of a real scenario and / or extreme values that would lead the trainee to handle an emergency scenario.

6.1.3 Survey management

During the execution of a Training Procedure, it is possible to present to the trainee a request to fill a survey; in order to perform this job, the Training Creation Tool introduces a new type of Action /

Relationship that will be catch by the Presentation Tool that will interrupt the training session, leaving proper time to the trainee to answer the questions. In this way the trainer can specify what the time required to enter the survey will be, without being forced to expose the feedback form only at the final phase of the training session.

6.1.4 Creation of the training session

The Training Creation Tool provides the ability to create training sessions, thus defining a training program for the trainee. The trainer can define training sessions simply by selecting, from the library of the training procedures, the most suitable ones to define the goal of the session under editing. This approach gives high flexibility to the training session concept, because a training procedure can be reused in multiple sessions, if it is useful for the purpose. According to this scenario, the library of the training procedures is composed by single, elementary, specific training tasks that could be arranged by the trainer in a more complex procedure finely tuned to fit the training needs of a specific individual.

6.2 AR TRAINING PRESENTATION TOOL (MOBILE VERSION)

The A.R. Training Presentation Tool is the customized version of A.R. Presentation Tool (PT) provided by the A.R. In-Factory Platform, designed to add specialized features to the Training and Educational Platform. The choice not to have a dedicated tool for the “on the job” training, has been done to exploit the powerful functionalities of the A.R. platform, by ensuring full compatibility with the A.R. OP Model, A.R. Creation Tool procedures, Data Analytics Tool integration and so on.

The customization of A.R. Training Presentation Tool is based on the following specialized features and configurations:

1. Training Session management.
2. Survey management.
3. Bidirectional Communication.
4. Data Log configuration.
5. VR-based simulated framework configuration.
6. User Interface customization.

6.2.1 Training Session Management

The A.R. Training Presentation Tool can manage at runtime the description of a training session created by the Training Creation Tool. In particular, the A.R. Training Presentation Tool allows to the trainee to select a specific training session, previously enabled by his trainer, and to sequentially load and activate the specific training procedures that make up the session. For each training procedure, the A.R. Training Presentation Tool provides all the presentation functionalities included in A.R. Presentation Tool, and collects the specific log data addressed to the Training Data Analytics, by including the identifier of the source session.

6.2.2 Survey Management

The A.R. Training Presentation Tool can manage at runtime the presentation and the interaction with the surveys, which are included in the training procedures by the A.R. Training Creation Tool. In particular, the A.R. Training Presentation Tool allows to break the currently executed procedure, in order to present to the trainee a survey that he has to fill and for which all results are collected and added to the other log data of the procedure. In this way, because all the log data are stored in CIDEM, both the Training Data Analytics Tool and the Collaboration Tool can be loaded and shown to the trainers. After a survey the A.R. Training Presentation Tool resumes the execution of the procedure from the step where it has been interrupted.

6.2.3 Bidirectional Communication

The aim of this module (detailed in the Training Platform API, in the second iteration of this deliverable) is to provide a bidirectional flow of knowledge and data, between the trainee and his trainer and/or between the novice and an expert. The A.R. Training Presentation Tool provides a specific integration with this module, developed as a software component compliant with the A.R. Training Presentation Tool architecture. In particular, the A.R. Training Presentation Tool allows to the trainee and/or trainer to break the currently executed procedures in order to exchange information and data between them (e.g. help, specific instructions not found in the training procedure, new media content, etc.). Also in this case, specific data related to performed communication are collected and stored for consultation by the Training Data Analytics Tool and/or Collaboration Tool.

6.2.4 Data Log configuration

The A.R. Training Presentation Tool can collect a large amount of information at runtime by using the Data Log Module provided by the Presentation Tool. Nevertheless, it's essential to configure this module in the A.R. Training Presentation Tool, in order to:

1. provide the exact grouping of the data directly relevant to the KPIs managed by Training Data Analytics Tool;
2. enable the logging of specific data related to the specialized features of the tool (e.g. Training Session ID, Bidirectional Communication events, Survey results, etc.).

6.2.5 VR-based Simulated Framework configuration

The A.R. Training Presentation Tool allows to the trainee to practice on a specific training procedure out of the real environment (thus “no on the job training”), by mainly exploiting the possibility of the Presentation Tool to provide the description of each action of a procedure in Virtual Reality when the proper content has been provided to the Creation Tool. The A.R. Training Presentation Tool, in particular, can be configured by means of the application settings, in order to present to the trainee an alternative training path, derived by removing all dependencies from the real context. This customization is mainly based on:

- a) the simplification of the UI handling the access to some specialized functionalities (e.g. Augmented Reality visualization);
- b) the change of the default running mode of the tool;
- c) the simulation of the querying of some specific values to Middleware (e.g. sensors) and/or CIDEM by using the manually fixed values introduced by the TCT;
- d) a specific selection/filter of the data collected during the “offline” execution of the training procedure, addressed to the Data Analytics Tool.

6.2.6 User Interface customization

In order to correctly manage all the additions listed above, the UI of the A.R. Training Presentation Tool has been modified and enriched, when compared with that of the PT. In fact, Survey Management, Training Session Management and Bidirectional Communication plugin have all introduced dedicated UI and also the VR-based simulated framework enables/disables specific information shown to the trainee by the UI in order to clarify what data are “hardcoded” and what data will dynamically change during an “on the job” training session.

6.3 AR TRAINING PRESENTATION TOOL (DESKTOP VERSION)

The Training Presentation Tool for desktop platform doesn't include substantial changes and/or improvements compared with the mobile version, previously described, of the same tool. Anyway it's useful to stress that each addition introduced by the Training Platform to the base tools provided by the A.R. platform (e.g. Training Session Management, Survey Management, Bidirectional Communication, etc.), has been declined in the desktop version of the Training Presentation tool, according to the availability of physical devices and interfaces.

6.4 AR TRAINING CUSTOM PRESENTATION TOOL

The Presentation Tools provide a rich set of visualization and interaction functionalities in order to present previously prepared A.R. SOP directly “on the job”. By using these tools, operators can follow a specific procedure step by step, obtain support for their current task, and choose the kind of information they want about the procedure, being able to choose the level of detail required.

The key features of the A.R. custom tool are:

1. Support to different target platforms.
2. High scalability on physical devices (e.g. desktop pc, mobile devices, wearable devices) and a large number of presentation modes (e.g. in Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, Speech only, Text only, hybrid, etc.).
3. The key features of the A.R. custom tool are:
 - 3.1. Support of assembly and maintenance operations in A.R. for the operational environment.
 - 3.2. Support to visualization of common or emergency indications to the operators, deriving from external modules (e.g. Integrated DSS)

The key Inputs of the A.R. custom tool are:

1. Augmented Reality Standard Operating Procedure.
2. Data obtained from Middleware module.
3. Data available from Integrated DSS and Event Managers modules.
4. Outputs provided:
 - 4.1. Audio/Visual information shown through implemented end user devices.
 - 4.2. Log file for each executed procedure.

The core purpose of the developed A.R. tool is the support of the assembly and maintenance using augmented reality and 3D model animation. The A.R. tool is able to monitor all the steps executed by an operator and translate them in an animated sequence of steps, using augmented reality and the 3D models of the used components. Based on the recording of the operation activities and recognition of objects, tools and movements, this application has all necessary components for the automatic creation of all the animations and sequence of operations that are presented in real time through augmented reality enable devices. Furthermore, instructions and 3D objects are also presented in augmented reality. The real time support and/or notifications are offering additional guidance to the employee. Covering the manufacturing assembly operations in real world scenarios based on SUNLIGHT manufacturing operations, all the correct procedures have been documented and have been developed in augmented reality.

The A.R. training custom presentation tool functionality of the manufacturing assembly operations comes to address identified needs described in the respective Use Cases^{1,2}. The visualization tool is based on the abstraction of the shop floor in terms of semantic IoT resources corresponding to “virtual entities”, as it was presented in the IoT Architecture Reference Model (ARM). Additionally, we added the required classes and interconnections supporting the Satisfactory applications.

To that end, all processed events will be used as input to the developed multi-sensorial framework for further analysis based on the developed data analytics algorithms. The A.R. tool enables the end user to see additional relevant data while working, or to reach a realistic experience while being trained in a simulated framework.

Furthermore, the A.R. tool was developed aiming to serve simultaneously two purposes, first of all to feed the Training Educational Environment and the Operational Platform with Augmented Intelligence and, second, to leverage and benefit from the newly proposed HMIs for the work shop floor (e.g. glasses). Therefore, A.R. tool is easily customizable and adaptable to the users' needs and preferences and supports gamification towards the attractiveness and adoption of the system by employees. Finally, the developed A.R. tool integrates and presents the Semantic Context and the Collaborative tools through an easy to use and intuitive interface.

Since Presentation Tools are stand-alone desktop applications and mobile apps, they can communicate with the other Satisfactory modules mainly via LinkSmart and/or its light version built in features provided by:

1. AR Glasses (by GlassUP).
2. Wearable Devices (by GlassUP and 3th parts).
3. Mobile Devices (for instance Tablet, Smartphones etc.).
4. Desktop PCs.

It also includes management of the following aspects:

1. Worker's Input:
 - 1.1. Touch [Type and Press] (e.g. Touch Screen of a Table, keyboard).
 - 1.2. Speech (e.g. Microphone).
 - 1.3. Body [body movement, gesture] (e.g. Camera, Motion Tracking System).
2. Output to Worker:
 - 2.1. Display (e.g. A.R. Glasses, Tablet display).
 - 2.2. Text to speech (e.g. Speakers, Headphones).
 - 2.3. Audio (e.g. Speakers, Headphones).

Therefore, the A.R. tool has the responsibility to provide dedicated customized services to support the activities of training and education to workers, machinery operators and manufacturing process supervisors. The initial goal is to manage, the creation of content for training and use. Therefore, the A.R. tool optimizes its effectiveness by focusing on the technologies of Augmented Reality, on the exploitation of a new generation of HMIs and on the "on the job" training approach.

One of the core functionalities are the verification of the customized manufacturing assembly operations and the 3D scene and objects recognition, then the presentation of an animated sequence of steps using augmented reality and 3D models. These representations are based on the translation of documented specific assembly manufacturing operations from SUNLIGHT manufactory. Regarding the development of the core algorithmic implementation, native programming language have been used being the next step the wrapping of the item developed in java in order to have a dynamic library that feeds a unity3D project where all the augmented reality components are being added. Technologies, platforms, libraries modules and specific versions used are presented in details in the respective deliverable.

Hence, for each operation, the sequence of steps is:

1. Identify assembly parts in scene and register 3D models of parts with the actual objects.
2. Show A.R. 3D animation of assembly operation.
3. Worker Performs assembly.
4. Custom A.R. Tool determines correct placement of parts.
5. If correct, proceed to next step of assembly, otherwise notify worker.

Figure 9 Automatic identification of 3D objects using A.R. custom tool (Battery from SUNLIGHT shop floor)

In short, the main objective of this functionality is the recognition of a real world 3D object (i.e. battery from SUNLIGHT manufactory), as shown in Figure 9, in order to render 3D model animations and translate the correct operation as an augmented reality representation where the end user could be able to follow activities performed in real time, verifying that they are consistent with the ones presented trough the A.R. tool.

Figure 10 Identify 3D objects and perform Virtual verification of different assembly operations

Furthermore, to the learning and supporting functionalities, a verification functionality of the performed operation is available for each one of the performed tasks, where workers are able to cross check the completed task of battery assembly and verify that they have followed the correct procedure (see figure 10).

Hence, with the responsibility to provide dedicated services to support the activities of training and education to workers, machinery operators and manufacturing process supervisors, this tool aims to manage, the creation of content for training and use for specific tasks.

Additional to the functionality inherited from the main A.R. platform, this component can provide specialized services, in order to increase the involvement of the trainees. Services such as:

1. Support to a bidirectional communication between the trainees and their supervisor (or, in general, between the novice and the expert), in order to increase the knowledge of the trainee.
2. Integration between components in order to support information and data transfer among the end user tools.
3. Management of implementation specific features for performance measurements and analysis of the observed performed operations.

More in details, in order to achieve the battery recognition and the A.R. presentation, a 7-step approach has been implemented and tested against several battery types within SUNLIGHT's shop floor. The proposed solution aims to extract meaningful information out of the captured frames and estimate the upper surface of the battery by performing the described pose estimation algorithms. In brief, the first step attempts to clean the input frames from noise by contrast enhancement, then two different processes are performed in parallel: one to detect the 3D object and the other to estimate the pose of the object. Next, with a multimodal approach, the extracted information from both processes are weighted in order to estimate the upper surface of the object. Finally, an affine transformation in the 2d and 3D animated objects is performed and then the objects are projected over the estimated surface.

AR Training Custom Presentation Tool operations for SUNLIGHT

Examples of A.R. training custom representation processes, for tasks with respect to battery assembly as it was recorded by CERTH/ITI in the SUNLIGHT's shop floor, is presented below. These operations, indicated in bold in the table below, are intended to demonstrate an example of how the A.R. custom tool was developed for a specific shop floor and not to list the current available functionalities. More in detail, the table below presents the supporting functionalities and steps for the A.R. training custom tool in order to provide efficient and effective end to end support and validation during the entire described operations. Therefore, workers are able to use the A.R. custom presentation tool for support and validation in steps of the performed operation that this feature is applicable.

	Recording Presentation	Duration/items	AR Tool used
1	Task instructions (topology and cell information)	3	AR Presentation Tool
2	Box-type selection based on performed task	2	AR Presentation Tool
3	Transfer and cell placement T fitting for transfer T encapsulation T elevation Cell movement over the box Cell placement Encapsulation removal T removal confirmation: polarity check	00:36	AR Presentation Tool + Custom A.R. Tool for battery cell polarity verification
4	Cell fluids completion (optional)		AR Presentation Tool
5	Original covering removal stopper placement	0:21	AR Presentation Tool
6	Bracket screw opening bridges mounting screw mounting	0:22 0:19	AR Presentation Tool
7	screw tightness (specific screwdriver)	0:15	AR Presentation Tool
8	torque control (torque wrench)	0:09	AR Presentation Tool
9	pipe fitting (optional - when auto aqua filling is needed)	00:45	AR Presentation Tool
10	capacity sensor placement (optional) tapping, sensor mounting, bridge connection confirmation: bridge connection	0:16 0:16	AR Presentation Tool + Custom A.R. Tool for bridge connection verification
11	labelling	0:34	AR Presentation Tool
12	Cleaning cells surfaces		AR Presentation Tool
13	Packaging	1	AR Presentation Tool
14	Ribbon, palletizing, wrapping		AR Presentation Tool

Table 1: battery assembly step descriptions

Verification process using A.R. custom presentation tool

Regarding the verification and in order to monitor the battery assembly operation, a 6-step approach has been implemented and tested against several battery types within SUNLIGHT's shop floor. The proposed solution aims to extract meaningful information out of a video clip and verify the battery assembly operation (figure 11) through iterative template matching. The overview of the proposed solution is graphically depicted below.

Hence, the final panorama image contains all the optical information captured within the video clip in a single image that can be further processed for the assembly operation verification. Initially, top view segmentation is performed to crop the regions of interest (battery top-view) and exclude the background areas (e.g. floor) from the next steps of the algorithm. For top view segmentation, the theory of super pixel segmentation is exploited. Super pixel segmentation algorithms are gaining in popularity over the last few years compared to pixel-based segmentations as they are contextually more meaningful components. Generally speaking, the pixel model leads to computationally expensive algorithms that are greatly affected by noise. Moreover, as an entity, a pixel is not perceptually meaningful but rather a sensor feature.

Figure 11 Confirm the correct assembly inside the detected area (in 2BSC4.1: cable connectivity for a specific type of battery)

Thereby, in order to adhere well to image boundaries and thus produce better segmentation results, super pixel segmentation offers an efficient high-level methodology for partitioning an image into homogenous areas. Simple Linear Iterative Clustering (SLIC) is an adaptation of k-means for super pixel segmentation that offers certain critical advantages over other super pixel segmentation algorithms. Namely, it's significantly faster, more memory efficient and improves the overall segmentation performance since it exhibits state-of-the-art boundary adherence.

Classified previous knowledge of battery types, stored within XML files allows performing iterative operations to identify the type of the segmented image. For Battery type identification a binary AND operation is performed between identified Hough lines (from the segmented top view) and expected battery partitioning (already known from parsing the battery types). The battery type with the greatest number of intersections is finally selected. The final step of the assembly verification algorithm (see figure 12) comprises a template matching approach for connector detection. We used 4 types of templates, two templates with vertical and two templates with horizontal

orientation. Identified connector positions from previous step are compared with connector expected positions from battery type information, stored within XML files, in an iterative way in order to detect possible errors in assembly process.

Figure 12 Validation of assembly operation

As it was described the objective of this tool is to increase the efficiency of the production facilities in the manufacturing shop floor in cases where general solutions are not applicable and a more customized solution is needed.

At the same time A.R. tool contributes in a positive way at the workload of workers in order to help them address evolving production requirements.

The A.R. tool provides semantically enhanced functionalities in order to enhance and facilitate the monitoring and supervision in real-time the specific evolving production processes.

To increase even more the productivity and flexibility of the workers involved in the production processes, the A.R. custom tool will provide functionalities for tasks only related to the respective manufacture operations.

Having previously fed the A.R. tool with real-time data streams from the correct evolution of the production cycle, the workers are provided with the ability to model dynamically the temporal dynamics of workplace occupancy with the aim of planning and balancing the workload density more efficiently.

To that end, and with respect to the described tasks on the respective deliverables, specific training needs were identified and used in combination with a group of case scenarios in order to

design the A.R. custom tool training models and interfaces to improve SUNLIGHT employee's knowledge and skills through the use of Augmented Reality technologies.

The modelling activities capitalizes on the experience of on training factory's personnel in various types of manufacturing procedures that not covered from the non-custom A.R. tool, and covers training areas, such as machinery monitoring, critical issues on certain manufacturing operations, maintenance procedures, including predictive, condition based and reactive maintenance as well as best practices for certain daily and periodic operations customized only for the SUNLIGHT shop floor operational needs.

Regarding the overall architecture A.R. custom tool is developed as an additional component on top of A.R. In-Factory Platform, but is able to take advantage of the specialized services offered by several other members of the Facility Layer and of the Middleware customized for the needs of the specific shop floor. Subsequently, due to this integration with the A.R. platform, the custom training component inherits all of its major functionalities such as:

1. Support to the description and presentation of procedures related to all areas required (Training, Manufacturing, Maintenance).
2. Support to the creation and use of standard procedures related both to common or planned activities, and to emergency situations.
3. Support to the creation of condition-based procedures.
4. Support to the services offered both on-the-job and in a simulated environment.
5. Use of specific content perfectly integrated into HMLs inherited by A.R. Tools.

Beyond the functionality inherited from the platform A.R., custom tool can provide several highly specialized services that are necessary in order to increase the level of involvement of the trainees, these are:

1. Support to a bidirectional communication between the trainees and their supervisor (or, in any case, between the novice and the expert), in order to increase the passage of knowledge.
2. Support to a transfer of information and data between the tools made available to the trainees and their supervisor.
3. Implementation of features specifically related to the management of a training session: performance measurement, comparison with previous sessions, analysis of results and provision of indices and specific information, etc.

From the point of view of its composition, the Training Platform includes a highly specialized tool for training, diversified into four variants to cover both physical configurations to support (GlassUP A.R. Devices, Mobile Devices) and the different roles of the user (trainee, supervisor). Different instances of the tool of training have the opportunity to communicate with each other, allowing it to provide the services described above. Also for the Training Platform, the description of training operating procedures is done through the tools developed for the platform of AR, namely: The A.R. Semantic Editor, A.R. OP Editor and A.R. OP "on the job" Editor. Overall, A.R. custom tool inherits all the described A.R. functionalities providing some customised additional support and verification abilities for the specific shop floor.

6.5 AR TRAINING ON MICROSOFT HOLOLENS

A customised version of the AR Presentation Tool is available for Microsoft HoloLens. This version supports the same core functionality found in the mobile and desktop versions. HoloLens is a head-mounted display that is able to project high-definition virtual content or holograms over real world objects. The main advantage of this setup is that it eliminates the need to hold a physical device (e.g. a tablet) so the trainee can use his hands freely in order to perform different activities. In contrast to other HMD solutions, HoloLens processing power allows the tool to run directly on the device without the need for another visualisation device.

Figure 13 Representation of HoloLens field of view and gaze functionality

The front of the device features a depth camera allowing the recording of the operation activities and recognition of objects, tools and movements. Worker's input is carried through gaze, gestures and speech. The output to the user is done through the device's display using Holographic presentations as well as by audio through the built in speakers.

By ROTATING his head the user navigates a virtual cursor and fills the required fields in the log-in screen. Text input is supported using a virtual keyboard. Selection is performed by the air tap gesture. HoloLens recognizes hand gestures by tracking the position of either or both hands that

Comment [TR6]:
Maybe it should be better use "rotating" and "moves" because the users navigate the virtual environment through the virtual cursor that it moves following the user's gaze, so the head rotation.

are visible to the device. HoloLens detects hands when they are in either the ready state (back of the hand facing you with index finger up) or the pressed state (back of the hand facing you with the index finger down). When hands are in other poses, the HoloLens will ignore them. Voice commands are also supported using the built in microphone.

Comment [TR7]: The HoloLens is an object, therefore it would be more appropriate using the verb "detect" instead "see"

Figure 14 Air tap gestures

The trainee can choose between any of the operative procedures and training sessions. The device supports the detection and tracking of markers, image and object targets. By selecting the AR mode from the UI, 3D models are displayed directly on the environment allowing for a more immersive experience for the user. The selection of the intended action is activated using the pre-defined gestures.

Figure 15 UI with a virtual keyboard and cursor

Figure 16 3D model in VR mode running on HoloLens Emulator

Figure17: UI and 3D model as seen through HoloLens device

7. PLATFORM COMPONENT: THE TRAINING DATA ANALYTICS TOOL

The evaluation of training in terms of its impact on the workers and its added value to the decision makers is crucial. The evaluation from the end user's point of view is examined in T5.2; Evaluation Methodology and Plans, using the tools developed within the aforementioned task. However, this evaluation may be subjective and is also related to the user acceptance and perception. It is noted that within the on-the-job training toolkit, a set of data/information is collected that can be used to assess the performance and impact of the training in a more subjective way. Moreover, this evaluation can be a strong selling point for the exploitation of the product in approaching and convincing the management to decide to select this part of the SatisFactory framework solution, as well as the workers to use it.

7.1 INFORMATION PROVIDED BY THE ON-THE-JOB PLATFORM

There are several data that can be provided by the On-the-job Training Platform and they can be enriched in the course of future developments.

In this stage and within the scope of the activity here described, an indicative list is provided below, in order to better showcase and understand the type of information that can be extracted and reused for the evaluation of the training procedure.

In the table below, the information is grouped in Categories and they are coupled with a type of event. Each piece of information can be associated to one or more of the following functions: training, production and maintenance. The idea is that the information used in training is applicable and reusable in other operations and that basic functionalities of this module can be replicated for other toolkits. Further, each information has been labelled according to its relevance to possible application fields that has been already identified in the context of the SatisFactory project: **T** is for training, **P** is for production, **M** is for maintenance

ID	Category	EventLogged	T	P	M
1	Time	Start	True	True	True
2	Time	Stop	True	True	True
3	Time	Pause	True	True	True
4	Time	Abort	True	True	True
5	UserInfo	Worker/trainee id	True	True	True
6	UserInfo	User role	True	True	True
7	UserInfo	User experience level	True	True	True
8	UserInfo	Department id	True	True	True
9	UserInfo	Worker experience level timestamp	True	True	True
10	UserInfo	Team Id	True	True	True
11	Collaboration	Caller/Callee UserInfo	False	False	False
12	Collaboration	Start call timestamp	False	False	False

13	Collaboration	End call timestamp	False	False	False
14	Collaboration	Direction	False	False	False
15	Collaboration	Collaboration Type	True	True	True
16	ExternalDataRequests	Data requested timestamp	True	True	True
17	ExternalDataRequests	Information requested	True	True	True
18	ExternalDataRequests	Data received timestamp	True	True	True
19	ExternalDataRequests	Information received	True	True	True
20	ExternalDataRequests	Data provider used	True	True	True
21	ProcedureInfo	Procedure id	True	True	True
22	SessionInfo	Procedure instance id	True	True	True
23	SessionInfo	Environment	True	True	True
24	TrainingInfo	User Info of who requested to start the session	True	False	False
25	Operation	Id	True	True	True
26	Step	Id	True	True	True
27	Action	Id	True	True	True
28	ProductionInfo	Production order id	False	True	True
29	ProductionInfo	Shift	False	True	True
30	MaintenancelInfo	Damaged machine/tool/component id	False	False	True
31	ExternalEvents	Received notification timestamp	True	True	True
32	ExternalEvents	Notification sender	True	True	True
33	ExternalEvents	Messaged notified	True	True	True
34	ExternalEvents	Notification type	True	True	True
35	UserNavigation	Action type	True	True	True
36	UserNavigation	Action timestamp	True	True	True
37	Feedback	User message	True	True	True
38	Feedback	Timestamp	True	True	True
39	Feedback	Feedback Type	True	True	True
40	Feedback	Severity	True	True	True
41	Survey	Survey question Id	True	True	True
42	Survey	Survey answer value	True	True	True
43	Conditions	Condition to evalutate	True	True	True
44	Conditions	Condition value	True	True	True
45	Conditions	Begin evaluation	True	True	True
46	Resource	Resource name	True	True	True
47	Resource	Begin use timestamp	True	True	True
48	Resource	Resource type	True	True	True
49	Conditions	Force	True	False	False
50	Conditions	Provider	True	True	True
51	Conditions	End evaluation	True	True	True

52	Resource	End use timestamp	True	True	True
53	Survey	Begin question	True	True	True
54	Survey	End question	True	True	True

Table 2 Information available through the On-the-job training toolkit

The following table provides notes to the previous one:

ID	Category	EventLogged	T	P	M
1	Time	Start	True	True	True
2	Time	Stop	True	True	True
3	Time	Pause	True	True	True
4	Time	Abort	True	True	True
5	UserInfo	Worker/trainee id	True	True	True
6	UserInfo	User role	True	True	True
7	UserInfo	User experience level	True	True	True
8	UserInfo	Department id	True	True	True
9	UserInfo	Worker experience level timestamp	True	True	True
10	UserInfo	Team Id	True	True	True
11	Collaboration	Caller/Callee UserInfo	False	False	False
12	Collaboration	Start call timestamp	False	False	False
13	Collaboration	End call timestamp	False	False	False
14	Collaboration	Direction	False	False	False
15	Collaboration	Collaboration Type	True	True	True
16	ExternalDataRequests	Data requested timestamp	True	True	True
17	ExternalDataRequests	Information requested	True	True	True
18	ExternalDataRequests	Data received timestamp	True	True	True
19	ExternalDataRequests	Information received	True	True	True
20	ExternalDataRequests	Data provider used	True	True	True
21	ProcedureInfo	Procedure id	True	True	True
22	SessionInfo	Procedure instance id	True	True	True
23	SessionInfo	Environment	True	True	True
24	TrainingInfo	User Info of who requested to start the session	True	False	False
25	Operation	Id	True	True	True
26	Step	Id	True	True	True
27	Action	Id	True	True	True
28	ProductionInfo	Production order id	False	True	True
29	ProductionInfo	Shift	False	True	True
30	MaintenancelInfo	Damaged machine/tool/component id	False	False	True

31	ExternalEvents	Received notification timestamp	True	True	True
32	ExternalEvents	Notification sender	True	True	True
33	ExternalEvents	Messaged notified	True	True	True
34	ExternalEvents	Notification type	True	True	True
35	UserNavigation	Action type	True	True	True
36	UserNavigation	Action timestamp	True	True	True
37	Feedback	User message	True	True	True
38	Feedback	Timestamp	True	True	True
39	Feedback	Feedback Type	True	True	True
40	Feedback	Severity	True	True	True
41	Survey	Survey question Id	True	True	True
42	Survey	Survey answer value	True	True	True
43	Conditions	Condition to evalutate	True	True	True
44	Conditions	Condition value	True	True	True
45	Conditions	Begin evaluation	True	True	True
46	Resource	Resource name	True	True	True
47	Resource	Begin use timestamp	True	True	True
48	Resource	Resource type	True	True	True
49	Conditions	Force	True	False	False
50	Conditions	Provider	True	True	True
51	Conditions	End evaluation	True	True	True
52	Resource	End use timestamp	True	True	True
53	Survey	Begin question	True	True	True
54	Survey	End question	True	True	True

Please, note the following about the data:

1. The data can be extracted in a CIDEM compliant xml format, so that they can be reused by other SatisFactory components, if required.
2. The data are currently a proposal that must be further discussed and refined in order to have a final set that could be used to drive the coding. Namely:
 - 2.1. New parameters could be identified if needed by the Data Analytics Tool.
 - 2.2. New values could be added to further define to the set of allowed ones.
3. The data are embodied in a XML format;
 - 3.1. an example of the XML structure could be found in the annex B, section 9.2.1;
 - 3.2. the format of that XML data is specified by means of the .xsd file referenced in the annex B, section 9.2.2.

7.2 TRANSFORMATION OF INFORMATION INTO KPIS

The next step is the transformation of this information into objective and measurable key performance indicators (KPIs) that can help to make comparison of the situation before and after the introduction of the new training system. A number of KPIs have been the result of brainstorming sessions until now, and they have been discussed among the technology providing partners involved, capitalising on the requirements of the end users, as they have been noted in *T1.1 End-user and shop floor, system requirements and specifications*.

At this stage of the development of the toolkit, a number of KPIs have been designed and they are being considered in terms of added value and ease of data extraction and their process will continue throughout M21-M25. The next planned step is to make the decision with all involved stakeholders for which KPIs to use in M26-M30.

The initially designed metrics that can be extracted in a straightforward way are shown in the table below as Training Assessment Factors (TAF). Additionally, other than the aforementioned **primary** Training Assessment Factors, there are also other aspects that can be considered, as subject of future developments, in close collaborations with *T2.3 Social interaction and gamification development to increase attractiveness* and *T5.2 Evaluation methodology and plans*. These are the Worker Factors (WF) related to worker satisfaction and acceptance of the SatisFactory solutions and the Decision Maker Factors (DMF) related to parameters considered of importance so that the decision makers can decide on the value, investment and adoption of the toolkit.

It should be mentioned that these factors may require information and interaction with other SatisFactory components, as well additional information from the shop floor or management levels. For these reasons, the metrics below could be extended in the future.

The list of the transformations, being quite long, is included in the attachment A. Please, refer to that section in order to know what KPI is associated with the data to be logged contributing to its definition.

7.3 PROCESSING OF INFORMATION

The main purpose of the training evaluation stage is to transform the data into information and knowledge or actionable knowledge (decision) according to the iteration shown in figure 13. In this stage the data has to be normalized and stored in a handy format. The stage is iterative, cycling between analysis and presentation of the results of analysis. Moreover, depending on the findings from each iteration cycle, as well as on remarks from the deployment on the shop floors, modifications may be needed.

Comment [TR8]: This should be updated

Comment [TR9]: Which table? Annex A?

Comment [TR10]: This should be updated if the development is complete

Figure 1: Iterative training evaluation

It is expected that after a number of iterations the KPIs will have been decided and the system will be stabilised. However, this module is being developed in a way that it can be adapted to the needs of each specific shop floor, following the business objectives of each company. The KPIs (definition, interconnection, applicable operation etc.) are kept in a database for ease of modification and interaction with the main system.

On the basis of the previous training experience gained by ABE, the calculated KPIs could be grouped, as a matter of convenience, into four categories/steps.

1. What Happened

In this category, all the KPIs that have to deal with the history of the training are included, such as which trainees have participated, what are the total hours spent, what is the effect of the training on the number and severity of accidents and alarms etc. This information will be presented with a series of charts and diagrams, in order to facilitate the perception of the evaluation via visualisation. Charts can be time-dependent charts, bar charts (in case of categories) or pie charts in case of percentages.

Comment [ADN11]: "have to deal" ?

2. Why it Happened

With this step, a relative presentation between KPIs is attempted. For example, it is important to know in what sections the training effort has led to improved performance or where the results were not SatisFactory enough. The training evaluation toolkit provides an easy way to correlate the KPI's according to each category. In order to accomplish that, the analysis phase offers a way to create a group of KPIs by M27. Moreover, a drill-down approach to a specific KPI can be offered (e.g. Machine failures per worker or alerts per worker).

3. Planning

In this step the analyst must make an assumption based on the previous observations. The prediction includes the desired results and the actions (concerning the training procedure) that will lead to that results. For that case the analysis tool will offer the ability to create a target. The target has to include a description, a time period, and specific range for one or more selected KPIs. For example, the prediction can be: For the next 6 months -10% in alerts KPI.

4. Evaluation

Finally, for the last step, the analyst must evaluate if the assumptions are educated and if the desired goals are met. To this end, the analysis tool will provide an easy way to determine visually, with a series of indicators, if the targets for the specific set of KPI's have been achieved.

7.4 SEMANTICS ENRICHMENT OF TRAINING ACTIVITY DATA

Besides being a cornerstone for defining a knowledge domain, the component called Ontology Manager, in short OM, will interact either directly or indirectly with several SatisFactory components, as thoroughly described in D3.1 (Semantically-enriched framework for analysis and design of dynamically evolving shop floor operations) and D2.1 (SatisFactory System Architecture), in order to empower the Satisfactory platform with analysis capabilities based on semantic technologies, which represent a key facet of the Factories of the Future, today more than ever.

Data gathered from many different sources will be stored in the SatisFactory repository according to CIDEM format, thus, enriched with semantics according to the semantic structures (ontologies) modelled and exposed through the Ontology Manager. The semantic interoperability (and integration) established between such two components (OM and CIDEM), then, allows the support for semantics enrichment of most of the SatisFactory static and dynamic data, for example the support to training data coming from the namesake component Training Data Analytics Tool (TDAT).

Figure 2: The OM-TDAT data exchange format is defined and ensured by the CIDEM.

The aim of the interaction between the Ontology Manager and the Training Data Analytics Tool is to enable a KPI-based interpretation of the training data by exploiting their meaning (semantic). The main expected benefits regarding the employment of semantic technologies to support the analysis of training data coming from the shop floor can be investigated by following a twofold approach that aims at analysing two equally important facets: contribution to knowledge and contribution to practice. Indeed, the interaction of the Satisfactory Ontology Manager (OM) and the Training Data Analytics Tool (TDAT), on the one hand aims to implement theoretical principles in the area of Knowledge Engineering (KE), exploit existing ontology models, which have been designed to support the analysis of dynamically evolving shop floor operations and the human resource optimization (see D2.2 and D3.1 for more on this). On the other hand, the KPI-based interpretation of the training data might lead to a deeper understanding of the latter, therefore, enriching the analysis carried out by the TDAT and widening the shop floor knowledge itself.

The list of terms as conceived in the SFO (SatisFactory Ontology) described in D2.2 has been extended with the following concepts: i) Training activity; ii) KPI, iii) KPI_Category, iii) KPI_Score; iv) KPI Type; v) KPI_Focus. These, together with the specification of their inter-links, represent the pillars of the trainee expertise evaluation (see Fig. 15).

Figure 17 Training Evaluation Ontology

The evaluation of the worker's expertise level exploits the semantic structure presented in Fig 16, In particular each instance of the KIP_Score should be perceived according to the following statement: *One trainer may have several KPI scores. The latter ubiquitously describes (refers to) one kind of KPI and one specific activity. The KPI score has a (xsd:double) value.*

Fig.16. Semantic structure of the KPI score

The quantitative evaluation of the training and the skill classification is addressed by the TDAT, however, in this framework, a conceptual evaluation approach based on Kirkpatrick's training evaluation model is presented. In particular, the first three levels are targeted, namely Reaction, Learning and Behaviour, and a weighted sum model (WSM) to quantify the impact of the training was proposed. However, there are three main limitations:

- The performance indicators (KPIs) identified for each level were based only on answers to questionnaires and not on data retrieved from the shop floor
- The KPIs were only at the level of the single trainee, with no KPIs to evaluate the performances of the team (i.e. Organizational level)
- No mechanism to evaluate the skill level of the trainee according to a pre-defined target and the performances of the other trainees was provided

Therefore, on this basis a set of KPIs based on data to be retrieved automatically from the shop floor was developed for each level of the Kirkpatrick's training evaluation model (i.e. Reaction, Learning, Behaviour, and Organization). Furthermore, a mechanism able to assign each trainee to a given skill level (Low, Medium, and High) based on the comparison with both a target level and the performances of the other trainees was designed.

In particular, on the basis of the KPIs identified, a summary indicator summarizing the overall performance of the trainee i at time j for the KPI k was defined:

$$P_{ijk} = \left[\left(\frac{V_{ijk}}{AV_{jk}} \right) * WR_{jk} + \left(\frac{V_{ijk}}{TV_{jk}} \right) * WA_{jk} \right] * 100$$

V_{ijk}/AV_{jk} is the ratio between the value of KPI k for employee i at time j (V_{ijk}) and the average of the values of KPI k of the n employees at time j (AV_{jk}). If this ratio is higher than 1 it means that the trainee i at time j for the KPI k is performing better than the average, if it is lower than 1 that is performing worse. V_{ijk}/TV_{jk} is the ratio between the value of KPI k for employee i at time j (V_{ijk}) and the target value of KPI k at time j (TV_{jk}) established by the management. If this ratio is higher than 1 it means that the trainee i at time j for the KPI k is performing better than the target value, if it is lower than 1 that is performing worse. WR_{jk} is the weight related to the Value/Average ratio while WA_{jk} is the weight related to the Value/Target ratio. These two weights can be balanced in order to give each time more importance to the performance of the single trainee compared with the average performance of the group or to the same performance compared with the pre-defined target value.

According to the value of P_{ijk} , each trainee i can be classified according to three different skill levels, namely Low, Medium and High. Considering as a reference all the values of KPI k of the n employees at time j , the trainee's skill level will be classified as Low if included between the zero and first quartile, as Medium if included between the first and third quartile and as High if included between the third and fourth quartile.

In order to aggregate the values of more KPIs for a given trainee i , standardized values of the single P_{ijk} should be used, in order to take into account different average and target values. As a consequence, for each P_{ijk} the following formula should be used:

$$Pstd_{ijk} = (P_{ijk} - AV_{jk})/SD_{jk}$$

, where SD_{jk} is the standard deviation of the values of KPI k of the n employees at time j . On this basis, the following aggregated performance of the trainee i at time j can be formulated:

$$AP_{ij} = \sum_{kj} \alpha_{kj} * Pstd_{ijk}$$

, where α_k is the weight related to the KPI k at time j . This way it is possible to evaluate the overall skill level of the trainee i at time j , by using the same approach described above. Finally, the overall performances of the single team/group can be easily obtained by means of the averages previously calculated for the different evaluation and temporal levels [ref 23].

Lastly, this is the last version of this document, which describes the effort spent during the first 30 months of the project and represents the final status of the activities carried out in T2.5 in order to investigate the potential interaction between the Semantic Framework and the On The Job Training Educational Platform. However, the statement and assumptions presented in the previous paragraphs should be perceived as a living asset that will grow while SatisFactory project continues toward its later stages.

Comment [ADN12]: D. Arena et al. (2017) An ontology-based model for training evaluation and skill classification in an Industry 4.0 environment. Advances in Production Management Systems (APMS) 2017 International Conference

8. CONCLUSIONS

8.1 THE CURRENT DEVELOPMENT

This document is about the description of the final achievements of the Task 2.5, which aims to design and implement a media rich training platform to be used to design, edit, deploy, serve and execute training operating procedures supported by the AR/VR presentations. Further, the task takes care of the overall training process defining a rich set of parameters that could be used to audit the training session, to compute, insightful KPIs to be used by a professional having an engineering profile in order to review and refine the training procedures used, making them more efficient, usable, enjoyable.

The aim of this deliverable was to present the development that ends at M30 of an innovative training system, making full use of A.R. rendering, able to support the improvement of the worker's skills making him / her more efficient and confident about the quality of the work to be done. The tool's capability is built atop of the A.R. in-factory platform, inheriting from it the ability to provide rich media content to the worker by means of examples, views, and instructions in a step by step procedure navigation which is, by design, friendly and comfortable in order to help in getting acquaintance with complex jobs. At the heart of the tools we have, as seen in the D4.3.2 [REF21] the training procedures to be used in the shop floor but, also, means to have a continuous training session quality improvement driven by the processing performed on the audit data made available in the logs.

If compared with the basic A.R. in-factory platform, we have not only more ancillary tools, like the Training Data Analytics Tool and its visualization capability, but also more platform features customized for a training platform; as example we have the capability to force sensor readings to assess the trainee reaction to predefined conditions coded when designing the procedure.

The AR training platform, in its basic configuration, was already available at the end of the first iteration. In this last iteration more specialized training capabilities are available in order to have the overall process able to run providing its payload and its feedback to the professionals designing the training procedures.

Comment [TR13]: M30?

Comment [TR14]: The VR rendering is not described in previous chapters.

8.2 THE NEXT ITERATION

The following activities have been completed at M30:

1. **Industrial, corporate and professional training: existing tools and formats, relationships with e-learning.** The existing training platforms and formats have been investigated in order to provide benchmarks and to establish if some form of interoperability between the on the job training and educational platform could be a plus. The analysis of the possible interplay between the Training Platform and the e-Learning platforms have been explored to look for possible opportunities;

Comment [TR15]: It should be updated

2. **Final list of audit data and related KPI.** The final list of the audit data and the KPI produced by the Training Data Analytics tool have been validated and made available taking in account the feedback provided on them by the software development phase.
3. **Training Data Analytics tool.** The training data analytics tool module has been released for operations. The core capability to transform audit data in true, high value information are now available, supporting a continuous quality improvement of the training procedures.
4. **Visualization tool for Training Data Analytics.** The Visual Training Data Analytics tool module has been released. It enables the operators to review and understand both raw KPI, produced by the Training Data Analytics tool, and the KPI produced by the semantic rules coded by means of the Ontology Manager.
5. **Training Session Management.** The full Training Session Management, affecting the Presentation tool and the Creation tool, has been released, making it possible create, edit, distribute, serve and execute training sessions built from libraries of training session procedures, including the capability to fill survey management along the procedure execution path.
6. **Semantic processing of the training data.** Example of rules to be used to process the KPI are provided and the inference engine able to perform the semantic processing of those rule is now available so that operators are able to get better insight about the training session completed.
7. **Verification functionalities.** In the second iteration of this deliverable, another custom A.R. tool is presented. It provides verification functionalities to enable the detection and recording of specific items, procedures and parameters relevant to CPERI's electromechanical facilities, so as to provide employees with support and verification capabilities of their customized operations within the scope of BSC5.1- Repair or restore an electromechanical malfunction.
8. **On-the-job-training.** The tools required to achieve the mission in the On-The-Job-Training scenario depicted in section 4 will be implemented.

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10. ANNEXES

10.1 ANNEX A: KPI/ LOG DATA ASSOCIATION

In this annex each KPI is associated with the data to be logged that contributes to its definition. Each KPI could be repeated several times in order to list all possible data related to it.

DMF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 2
Reduction of alarms			
Measures the number of alarms occurred compared to the number of alarms occurred before the use of the platform			
DMF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 3
Reduction of number of accidents			
Measures the total number of accidents compared to the total number of accidents occurred before the use of the platform			
DMF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 4
Reduction of severity of accidents			
Measure the average severity of accidents compared to the average severity of accidents occurred before the use of the platform			
DMF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 5
Productivity			
Assessment of which shift/team/production line is more or less productive, after a series of training sessions has been completed and a specific period of time has elapsed, according to business objectives. This metric lies outside of the system.			
DMF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 6
Worker turnover rate			
The system allows to log the workers id for each session, so this is an information can be assessed after the specific time frame requested by a specific company.			
DMF	Maintenance	Numeric	KPI ID: 11
Machine/Equipment that most failures occur			
Comparison of the failures in certain pieces of equipment before and after a series of training sessions has been completed and a specific period of time has elapsed, according to business objectives. Metric outside of the on-the-job training system (iDSS			
DMF	Production	Numeric	KPI ID: 7
Average order fulfilment cycle time			
Measures the average time spent to complete a production cycle			

DMF	Production	Numeric	KPI ID: 8
Average procedure completion time			
Measures the average time spent to complete a procedure			
DMF	Production	Numeric	KPI ID: 10
Amount of re-works			
Comparison of the reworks on certain pieces of equipment before and after a series of training sessions has been completed and a specific period of time has elapsed, according to business objectives. Metric outside of the on-the-job training system (iDSS)			
DMF	Production	Percentage	KPI ID: 9
Delivery In Full, On Time (DIFOT) Rate			
Mesaures the percentage of orders completed on time relative to the total of orders			
TAF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 12
Amount of repetetions per procedure's action			
Measures the number of repetitions of a certain action			
TAF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 13
The number of times a worker regeusted help from a supervisor			
Measure the number of times a worker regeusted help from a supervisor			
TAF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 14
Which "action" has been repeated the most time			
Measures the action which has been repeated the most time consecutively			
TAF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 15
Average time required to finish a certain action			
Measures the average time of execution for a procedure's action			
TAF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 16
Times that a novice worker repeats an action			
Measures the number of times a novice worker repeats a certain action in a procedure			
TAF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 17
Times that an experienced worker repeats an action			
Measures the number of times an expert worker repeats a certain action in a procedure			
TAF	All	Percentage	KPI ID: 18
Percentage of procedures drop outs			
Measures the number of times a procedure has been aborted relative to the total number of sessions			
TAF	All	Percentage	KPI ID: 19
Usage's percentage of the information stored in the repository			
Measures the percentage of usage of the different information stored in the repository			

TAF	All	Percentage	KPI ID: 20
Usage's percentage of the information retrieved from the middleware			
Measures the percentage of usage of the data providers in the middleware environment			
TAF	Training	Currency	KPI ID: 31
Average training cost per full time equivalent			
Measures the average amount spent on training for each full time equivalent (FTE) in the measurement period			
TAF	Training	Currency	KPI ID: 33
Human resources budget spent on training			
Measures how much of the HR budget is directed to training expenses			
TAF	Training	Currency	KPI ID: 41
Total cost of training per "time"			
Measures the total cost of training in a certain period of time			
TAF	Training	Currency	KPI ID: 50
Average training cost per hour			
Measures the average amount of money spent for every hour of training			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 21
Time spent on training			
Measures the number of hours spent training employees			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 22
Number of novice workers trained			
Measures the number of novice workers trained on a procedure			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 23
Number of experienced workers trained			
Measures the number of expert workers trained on a procedure			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 24
Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by himself/herself			
Measures the number of times a novice worker requested to repeat a training session			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 25
Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by his/her supervisor			
Measures the number of times a novice worker has been requested to repeat a training session by a supervisor			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 26
Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by himself/herself			
Measures the number of times an expert worker requested to repeat a training session			

TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 27
Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by his/her supervisor			
Measures the number of times an expert worker has been requested to repeat a training session by a supervisor			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 28
Frequency of trainings per department			
Measures the number of training sessions held for each department in a certain period of time			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 29
Amount of training per department			
Measures the number of training sessions held for each department			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 32
Average training hours per full time equivalent			
Measures the volume of training received by each full time equivalent (FTE) in a given time period			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 34
Training sessions for personnel			
Measures the number of training sessions held for every worker			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 36
Training sessions held for expert workers			
Measures the number of training sessions held for experienced workers			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 37
Training sessions held for novice workers			
Measures the number of training sessions held for novice workers			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 39
Average time to competence			
Measures the average time it takes until the expected competence level is reached by employees. The measurement can be done through various tests, interviews and surveys.			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 44
Training duration per "period" of time			
Measures the average length of a training session during the measurement period of time			
TAF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 46
Total hours employees spend in mentoring			
Measures the amount of hours spent by the employees in mentoring activities (training session, time spent in responding to help requests)			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 30
Percentage of training sessions drop outs			
Measures the number of times a training session has been aborted relative to the total number of			

training sessions			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 35
Training return on investment			
Measures the report between net benefit and costs per training session			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 38
Employees trained			
Measures the percentage of employees that have been trained			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 40
Training penetration rate			
Measures the percentage of employees completing specific training session compared to total number of employees to be trained			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 42
Employees above competence			
Measures the number of employees with good competency scores relative to the total number of assesses employees.			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 43
Employees below competence			
Measures the number of employees with poor competency scores relative to the total number of of assesses employees.			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 45
Employees cross-trained			
Measures the percentage of employees that received cross-training			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 47
Training sessions by procedure			
Measuere the training sessions spent for a particular procedure as a percentage of the total training sessions			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 48
Employees that have improved skills during a time period			
Measures the number of employees who proved to have improved their skills in a certain period of time as a result of training sessions relative to the total number of trained employees			
TAF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 49
Competence development expense out of payroll cost			
Measures the organization expense with employees competence development relative to the payroll expense during the reporting period of time			
WF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 51
Worker complaints			
Measures the number of compliants made by workers			

WF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 52
Reduction of work related stress			
Measures the level of stress perceived by workers (value requested through surveys) compared to the level of stress perceived by workers before the use of the platform			
WF	All	Numeric	KPI ID: 53
Worker engagement			
The perception of user/worker engagement may be differently viewed by each end user. Options may be the frequency that a worker or a team of workers uses the on-the-job training platform, the number of non-compulsory training sessions attended, the number			
WF	Training	Numeric	KPI ID: 54
Employee satisfaction with training			
Measures the general employee satisfaction with the quality, efficiency and effectiveness of the training programs			
WF	Training	Percentage	KPI ID: 55
Training channel delivery mix			
Measures the distribution of specific media (documentation, A.R. models, text, audio, video, images) as percentage of the total number of media made available			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 2	
KPI Definition: Reduction of alarms			
Data used: User message			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 2	
KPI Definition: Reduction of alarms			
Data used: Feedback Type			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 2	
KPI Definition: Reduction of alarms			
Data used: Severity			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 2	
KPI Definition: Reduction of alarms			
Data used: Timestamp			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 3	
KPI Definition: Reduction of number of accidents			
Data used: User message			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 3	
KPI Definition: Reduction of number of accidents			
Data used: Timestamp			
Category: DMF		KPI ID: 3	
KPI Definition: Reduction of number of accidents			

Data used: Feedback Type	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 3
KPI Definition: Reduction of number of accidents	
Data used: Severity	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 4
KPI Definition: Reduction of severity of accidents	
Data used: User message	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 4
KPI Definition: Reduction of severity of accidents	
Data used: Timestamp	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 4
KPI Definition: Reduction of severity of accidents	
Data used: Feedback Type	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 4
KPI Definition: Reduction of severity of accidents	
Data used: Severity	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 5
KPI Definition: Productivity	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 5
KPI Definition: Productivity	
Data used: Department id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 5
KPI Definition: Productivity	
Data used: Team Id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 5
KPI Definition: Productivity	
Data used: Shift	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 6
KPI Definition: Worker turnover rate	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 7
KPI Definition: Average order fulfilment cycle time	
Data used: Start	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 7

KPI Definition: Average order fulfilment cycle time	
Data used: Stop	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 7
KPI Definition: Average order fulfilment cycle time	
Data used: Production order id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 8
KPI Definition: Average procedure completion time	
Data used: Start	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 8
KPI Definition: Average procedure completion time	
Data used: Stop	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 8
KPI Definition: Average procedure completion time	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 9
KPI Definition: Delivery In Full, On Time (DIFOT) Rate	
Data used: Start	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 9
KPI Definition: Delivery In Full, On Time (DIFOT) Rate	
Data used: Stop	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 9
KPI Definition: Delivery In Full, On Time (DIFOT) Rate	
Data used: Production order id	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 10
KPI Definition: Amount of re-works	
Data used: Stop	
Category: DMF	KPI ID: 11
KPI Definition: Machine/Equipment that most failures occur	
Data used: Damaged machine/tool/component id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 12
KPI Definition: Amount of repetitions per procedure's action	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 12
KPI Definition: Amount of repetitions per procedure's action	
Data used: Id	

Category: TAF	KPI ID: 13
KPI Definition: The number of times a worker requested help from a supervisor	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 13
KPI Definition: The number of times a worker requested help from a supervisor	
Data used: User role	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 13
KPI Definition: The number of times a worker requested help from a supervisor	
Data used: Request Type	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 14
KPI Definition: Which "action" has been repeated the most time	
Data used: Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 15
KPI Definition: Average time required to finish a certain action	
Data used: Start	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 15
KPI Definition: Average time required to finish a certain action	
Data used: Stop	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 15
KPI Definition: Average time required to finish a certain action	
Data used: Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 16
KPI Definition: Times that a novice worker repeats an action	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 16
KPI Definition: Times that a novice worker repeats an action	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 16
KPI Definition: Times that a novice worker repeats an action	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 16
KPI Definition: Times that a novice worker repeats an action	
Data used: Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 17
KPI Definition: Times that an experienced worker repeats an action	

Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 17
KPI Definition: Times that an experienced worker repeats an action	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 17
KPI Definition: Times that an experienced worker repeats an action	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 17
KPI Definition: Times that an experienced worker repeats an action	
Data used: Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 18
KPI Definition: Percentage of procedures drop outs	
Data used: Abort	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 18
KPI Definition: Percentage of procedures drop outs	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 19
KPI Definition: Usage's percentage of the information stored in the repository	
Data used: Data requested timestamp	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 19
KPI Definition: Usage's percentage of the information stored in the repository	
Data used: Information requested	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 19
KPI Definition: Usage's percentage of the information stored in the repository	
Data used: Data provider used	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 20
KPI Definition: Usage's percentage of the information retrieved from the middleware	
Data used: Data requested timestamp	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 20
KPI Definition: Usage's percentage of the information retrieved from the middleware	
Data used: Information requested	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 20
KPI Definition: Usage's percentage of the information retrieved from the middleware	
Data used: Data provider used	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 21

KPI Definition: Time spent on training	
Data used: Start	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 21
KPI Definition: Time spent on training	
Data used: Stop	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 21
KPI Definition: Time spent on training	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 22
KPI Definition: Number of novice workers trained	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 22
KPI Definition: Number of novice workers trained	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 22
KPI Definition: Number of novice workers trained	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 22
KPI Definition: Number of novice workers trained	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 23
KPI Definition: Number of experienced workers trained	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 23
KPI Definition: Number of experienced workers trained	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 23
KPI Definition: Number of experienced workers trained	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 23
KPI Definition: Number of experienced workers trained	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 24
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	

Category: TAF	KPI ID: 24
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 24
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 24
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: User Info of who requested to start the session	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 25
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 25
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 25
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 25
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by a novice worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: User Info of who requested to start the session	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 26
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 26
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 26
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker	

requested by himself/herself	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 26
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by himself/herself	
Data used: User Info of who requested to start the session	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 27
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 27
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 27
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 27
KPI Definition: Number of repetitions of the training session made by an experienced worker requested by his/her supervisor	
Data used: User Info of who requested to start the session	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 28
KPI Definition: Frequency of trainings per department	
Data used: Department id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 28
KPI Definition: Frequency of trainings per department	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 28
KPI Definition: Frequency of trainings per department	
Data used: Environment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 29
KPI Definition: Amount of training per department	
Data used: Department id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 29
KPI Definition: Amount of training per department	
Data used: Procedure instance id	

Category: TAF	KPI ID: 29
KPI Definition: Amount of training per department	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 30
KPI Definition: Percentage of training sessions drop outs	
Data used: Abort	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 30
KPI Definition: Percentage of training sessions drop outs	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 30
KPI Definition: Percentage of training sessions drop outs	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 31
KPI Definition: Average training cost per full time equivalent	
Data used: Start	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 31
KPI Definition: Average training cost per full time equivalent	
Data used: Stop	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 31
KPI Definition: Average training cost per full time equivalent	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 31
KPI Definition: Average training cost per full time equivalent	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 32
KPI Definition: Average training hours per full time equivalent	
Data used: Start	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 32
KPI Definition: Average training hours per full time equivalent	
Data used: Stop	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 32
KPI Definition: Average training hours per full time equivalent	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 32
KPI Definition: Average training hours per full time equivalent	

Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 32
KPI Definition: Average training hours per full time equivalent	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 34
KPI Definition: Training sessions for personnel	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 34
KPI Definition: Training sessions for personnel	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 34
KPI Definition: Training sessions for personnel	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 36
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for expert workers	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 36
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for expert workers	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 36
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for expert workers	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 36
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for expert workers	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 37
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for novice workers	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 37
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for novice workers	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 37
KPI Definition: Training sessions held for novice workers	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 37

KPI Definition: Training sessions held for novice workers	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 38
KPI Definition: Employees trained	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 38
KPI Definition: Employees trained	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 38
KPI Definition: Employees trained	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 39
KPI Definition: Average time to competence	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 39
KPI Definition: Average time to competence	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 39
KPI Definition: Average time to competence	
Data used: Worker experience level timestamp	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 40
KPI Definition: Training penetration rate	
Data used: Start	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 40
KPI Definition: Training penetration rate	
Data used: Stop	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 40
KPI Definition: Training penetration rate	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 40
KPI Definition: Training penetration rate	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 40
KPI Definition: Training penetration rate	
Data used: Procedure instance id	

Category: TAF	KPI ID: 40
KPI Definition: Training penetration rate	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 42
KPI Definition: Employees above competence	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 42
KPI Definition: Employees above competence	
Data used: Question/Survey Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 42
KPI Definition: Employees above competence	
Data used: Question/Survey score	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 43
KPI Definition: Employees below competence	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 43
KPI Definition: Employees below competence	
Data used: Question/Survey Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 43
KPI Definition: Employees below competence	
Data used: Question/Survey score	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 44
KPI Definition: Training duration per "period" of time	
Data used: Start	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 44
KPI Definition: Training duration per "period" of time	
Data used: Stop	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 44
KPI Definition: Training duration per "period" of time	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 44
KPI Definition: Training duration per "period" of time	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 44
KPI Definition: Training duration per "period" of time	

Data used: User Info of who requested to start the session	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 45
KPI Definition: Employees cross-trained	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 45
KPI Definition: Employees cross-trained	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 45
KPI Definition: Employees cross-trained	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 45
KPI Definition: Employees cross-trained	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: User role	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: Caller/Callee UserInfo	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: Start call timestamp	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: End call timestamp	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46
KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: Direction	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 46

KPI Definition: Total hours employees spend in mentoring	
Data used: Request Type	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 47
KPI Definition: Training sessions by procedure	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 47
KPI Definition: Training sessions by procedure	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 47
KPI Definition: Training sessions by procedure	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 48
KPI Definition: Employees that have improved skills during a time period	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 48
KPI Definition: Employees that have improved skills during a time period	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 48
KPI Definition: Employees that have improved skills during a time period	
Data used: Worker experience level timestamp	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 48
KPI Definition: Employees that have improved skills during a time period	
Data used: Question/Survey Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 48
KPI Definition: Employees that have improved skills during a time period	
Data used: Question/Survey score	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 49
KPI Definition: Competence development expense out of payroll cost	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 49
KPI Definition: Competence development expense out of payroll cost	
Data used: User experience level	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 49
KPI Definition: Competence development expense out of payroll cost	
Data used: Worker experience level timestamp	

Category: TAF	KPI ID: 49
KPI Definition: Competence development expense out of payroll cost	
Data used: Question/Survey Id	
Category: TAF	KPI ID: 49
KPI Definition: Competence development expense out of payroll cost	
Data used: Question/Survey score	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 51
KPI Definition: Worker complaints	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 51
KPI Definition: Worker complaints	
Data used: Feedback Type	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 52
KPI Definition: Reduction of work related stress	
Data used: Question/Survey Id	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 52
KPI Definition: Reduction of work related stress	
Data used: Question/Survey score	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 53
KPI Definition: Worker engagement	
Data used: Worker/trainee id	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 53
KPI Definition: Worker engagement	
Data used: Procedure id	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 53
KPI Definition: Worker engagement	
Data used: Procedure instance id	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 53
KPI Definition: Worker engagement	
Data used: Enviroment	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 53
KPI Definition: Worker engagement	
Data used: User Info of who requeusted to start the session	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 54
KPI Definition: Employee satisfaction with training	

Data used: Question/Survey Id	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 54
KPI Definition: Employee satisfaction with training	
Data used: Question/Survey score	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 55
KPI Definition: Training channel delivery mix	
Data used: Resource name	
Category: WF	KPI ID: 55
KPI Definition: Training channel delivery mix	
Data used: Resource type	

ANNEX B: AUDIT XML FILE SPECIFICATIONS

In this paragraph we provide the XML specifications for the log file intended to support audit and to provide input to the training data analytics tool. As part of the specification is included the schema definition file.

10.1.1 Categories

In the following tables are shown the xml nodes that will be used to log the data listed in the 6.1 Section. Categories are the xml nodes that group information of the same type. This nodes have no value but only contain child nodes. Categories can be nested.

ID	Node Name	Example	Description
0	Session	<session> </session>	This is the root node
1	User	<user></user>	The node containing user's info
2	collaboration	<collaboration></collaboration>	The node containing collaboration's info
3	externalData	<externalData></externalData>	The node containing information on external data requests
4	procedure	<procedure></procedure>	The node containing the procedure's general info
5	Operation	<operation></operation>	The node containing operation's info
6	Step	<step></step>	The node containing step'info
7	Action	<action></action>	The node containing action's info
8	production	<production></production>	The node containing production's info
9	maintenance	<maintenance></maintenance>	The node containing maintenance general info
10	externalEvent	<externalEvent></externalEvent>	The node containing external events' info
11	userNavigation	<userNavigation></userNavigation>	The node containing user navigation info
12	Feedback	<feedback></feedback>	The node containing user feedback's info
13	Condition	<condition></condition>	The node containing condition's info
14	Resource	<resource></resource>	The node containing resource's

			info
15	Training	<training></training>	The node containing training's general info
16	survey	<survey></survey>	The node containing survey's info

10.1.2 Values

This table contains all the xml nodes that will store an actual value. For each node is specified to which data it's referred (6.1 Table2 ref.), to which category it belongs (Category column), its type and format (Value Type and Format columns), a proposed set of values for enum data types (Values column), an example of use (Example column) and the description.

Some of the values could be a duplicate, if the data are correctly stored on CIDEM (for example: user data), but they are included to increase the queries' efficiency. Proper definition of the possible values for enum type data is still open and should be further discussed.

The information to be logged could change when the components are released because, depending on their implementation, the available format may change.

ID: 0	ID-Recap: NULL	Node name: date	Category: 0
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<date>2016-10-04 14:00:00</date>		
Description	The audit session timestamp		

ID: 1	ID-Recap: 1,12,16,45,47,53	Node name: start	Category: multiple
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<start>2016-10-04 14:00:00</start>		
Description	The parent's event starting time		

ID: 2	ID-Recap: 2,13,18,51,52,54	Node name: stop	Category: multiple
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<stop>2016-10-04 14:00:00</stop>		
Description	The parent's event stop time		

ID: 3	ID-Recap: 3	Node name: pause	Category: 6
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<pause>2016-10-04 14:00:00</pause>		
Description	The parent's event pause time		

ID: 4	ID-Recap: 4	Node name: abort	Category: 4
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<abort>2016-10-04 14:00:00</abort>		
Description	The parent's event abort time		

ID: 5	ID-Recap: 5,11,24	Node name: id	Category: 1
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<id>user0</id>		
Description	User's id		

ID: 6	ID-Recap: 6,11,24	Node name: role	Category: 1
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	worker, trainee, trainer, supervisor, maintenance expert, ???		
Example:	<role>worker</role>		
Description	User's role		

ID: 7	ID-Recap: 7,11,24	Node name: experience	Category: 1
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	novice, expert, ???		
Example:	<experience>novice</experience>		
Description	User's experience level		

ID: 8	ID-Recap: 8,11,24	Node name: department	Category: 1
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<department>department0</department>		
Description	User's department		

ID: 9	ID-Recap: 9,11,24	Node name: levelUp	Category: 1
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<levelUp>2016-10-04 14:00:00</levelUp>		
Description	Last user's experience level advancement's timestamp		

ID: 10	ID-Recap: 10,11,24	Node name: team	Category: 1
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<team>team0</team>		
Description	User's team		

ID: 11	ID-Recap: 14	Node name: direction	Category: 2
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	in,out		
Example:	<direction>in</direction>		
Description	Collaboration's direction (calling someone, called by someone)		

ID: 12	ID-Recap: 15	Node name: type	Category: 2
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	help,information,???		
Example:	<type>help</type>		

Description	Collaboration's type		
ID: 13	ID-Recap:17	Node name: request	Category:3
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<request>condition0_threshold</request>		
Description	The external information requested		
ID: 14	ID-Recap:19	Node name: response	Category:3
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<response>25</response>		
Description	The external information returned		
ID: 15	ID-Recap:20	Node name: dataProvider	Category:3
Value type:	string	Format:	"system";"specific provider"
Values:	CIDEM;"table name" - MIDDLEWARE;"provider id"		
Example:	<dataProvider>cidem;Settings</dataProvider>		
Description	The request's target		
ID: 16	ID-Recap:21	Node name: id	Category:4
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<id>procedure0</id>		
Description	The procedure's id		

ID: 17	ID-Recap: 22	Node name: instance	Category: 0
Value type:	string	Format:	GUID
Values:			
Example:	<instance>1f1aac36-b718-40c2-8b37-9d816514b30a</instance>		
Description	The procedure's instance id		

ID: 18	ID-Recap: 23	Node name: environment	Category: 0
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	training,production,maintenance		
Example:	<environment>training</environment>		
Description	The procedure's environment		

ID: 19	ID-Recap: 25	Node name: id	Category: 5
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<id>operation0</id>		
Description	The operation's id		

ID: 20	ID-Recap: 26	Node name: id	Category: 6
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<id>step0</id>		
Description	The step's id		

ID: 21	ID-Recap: 27	Node name: id	Category: 7
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<id>action0</id>		
Description	The action's id		

ID: 22	ID-Recap: 28	Node name: order	Category: 8
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<order>order0</order>		
Description	The production order number carried out in the session		

ID: 23	ID-Recap: 29	Node name: shift	Category: 8
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<shift>1</shift>		
Description	The working shift		

ID: 24	ID-Recap: 30	Node name: defected	Category: 9
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<defected>Scanner2</defected>		
Description	The defected component's id		

ID: 25	ID-Recap: 31	Node name: receivedTime	Category: 10
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<receivedTime>2016-10-04 14:00:00</receivedTime>		
Description	The external event arrival's timestamp		

ID: 26	ID-Recap: 33	Node name: message	Category: 10
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<message>Fire alarm department0</message>		
Description	The received message		

ID: 27	ID-Recap: 34	Node name: type	Category: 10
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	warning,alarm,???		
Example:	<type>warning</type>		
Description	The notification's type		

ID: 28	ID-Recap: 32	Node name: sender	Category: 10
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:	incident detection system, DSS, ???		
Example:	<sender>DSS</sender>		
Description	The component sending the notification		

ID: 29	ID-Recap: 35	Node name: type	Category: 11
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	redo, previous, next, abort		
Example:	<type>next</type>		
Description	The user's action type		

ID: 30	ID-Recap:36	Node name: actionTime	Category:11
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<actionTime>2016-10-04 14:00:00</actionTime>		
Description	When the user done the action		

ID: 31	ID-Recap:37	Node name: message	Category:12
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<message>Main tool broken</message>		
Description	The message sent from the user		

ID: 32	ID-Recap: 38	Node name: notificationTime	Category: 12
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<notificationTime>2016-10-04 14:00:00</notificationTime>		
Description	The notification's timestamp		

ID: 33	ID-Recap: 39	Node name: type	Category: 12
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	note, malfuction, safety issue, accident, complain, alarm, survey ???		
Example:	<type>malfuction</type>		
Description	The notification's type		

ID: 34	ID-Recap: 40	Node name: severity	Category: 12
Value type:	enum	Format:	
Values:	list of severities?		
Example:	<severity>1</severity>		
Description	The notification's severity		

ID: 35	ID-Recap: 41	Node name: question	Category: 16
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<question>question0</question>		
Description	The question's id (for surveys)		

ID: 36	ID-Recap: 42	Node name: answer	Category: 16
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<answer>answer0</answer>		

Description	The answer's id		
ID: 37	ID-Recap: 43	Node name: conditionString	Category: 13
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<conditionString>Sensor0 > 25</conditionString>		
Description	The condition to evaluate		
ID: 38	ID-Recap: 44	Node name: value	Category: 13
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<value>22</value>		
Description	The value used in the condition evaluation		
ID: 39	ID-Recap: 49	Node name: forced	Category: 13
Value type:	bool	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<forced>>false</forced>		
Description	True if the value is forced by the user (due to a middleware problem)		

ID: 40	ID-Recap: 50	Node name: provider	Category: 13
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<provider>Sensor0</provider>		
Description	The value provider id (user id if forced)		
ID: 41	ID-Recap: 45	Node name: conditionTime	Category: 13
Value type:	timestamp	Format:	YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS
Values:			
Example:	<conditionTime>2016-10-04 14:00:00</conditionTime>		
Description	The condition evaluation's timestamp		
ID: 42	ID-Recap: 46	Node name: name	Category: 14
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<name>video0</name>		
Description	The resource file's name		
ID: 43	ID-Recap: 48	Node name: type	Category: 14
Value type:	string	Format:	
Values:			
Example:	<type>video</type>		
Description	The resource's type		

10.1.3 XSD audit file definition

This is the current xml schema for the audit file:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<xs:schema attributeFormDefault="unqualified" elementFormDefault="qualified"
xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema">
  <xs:element name="session">
    <xs:complexType>
```



```
<xs:sequence>
  <xs:element name="instance" type="xs:string" />
  <xs:element name="date" type="xs:string" />
  <xs:element name="user">
    <xs:complexType>
      <xs:sequence>
        <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
        <xs:element name="role" type="xs:string" />
        <xs:element name="experience" type="xs:string" />
        <xs:element name="department" type="xs:string" />
        <xs:element name="levelUp" type="xs:string" />
        <xs:element name="team" type="xs:string" />
      </xs:sequence>
    </xs:complexType>
  </xs:element>
  <xs:element name="environment" type="xs:string" />
  <xs:element name="training" minOccurs="0">
    <xs:complexType>
      <xs:sequence>
        <xs:element name="user">
          <xs:complexType>
            <xs:sequence>
              <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
              <xs:element name="role" type="xs:string" />
              <xs:element name="experience" type="xs:string" />
              <xs:element name="department" type="xs:string" />
              <xs:element name="levelUp" type="xs:string" />
              <xs:element name="team" type="xs:string" />
            </xs:sequence>
          </xs:complexType>
        </xs:element>
      </xs:sequence>
    </xs:complexType>
  </xs:element>
  <xs:element name="production" minOccurs="0">
    <xs:complexType>
```



```
<xs:sequence>
  <xs:element name="order" type="xs:string" />
  <xs:element name="shift" type="xs:string" />
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="maintenance" minOccurs="0">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="defected" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="procedure">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="operation" maxOccurs="unbounded">
        <xs:complexType>
          <xs:sequence>
            <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
            <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
            <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
            <xs:element name="step" maxOccurs="unbounded">
              <xs:complexType>
                <xs:sequence>
                  <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
                  <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
                  <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
                  <xs:element maxOccurs="unbounded" name="action">
                    <xs:complexType>
                      <xs:sequence>
                        <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
                        <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
```



```
<xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
<xs:element name="externalData" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="request" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="response" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="dataProvider" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="condition" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="conditionString" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="value" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="forced" type="xs:boolean" />
      <xs:element name="provider" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="collaboration" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="direction" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="type" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="user">
        <xs:complexType>
          <xs:sequence>
            <xs:element name="id" type="xs:string" />
            <xs:element name="role" type="xs:string" />
          </xs:sequence>
        </xs:complexType>
      </xs:element>
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
```



```
<xs:element name="experience" type="xs:string" />
<xs:element name="department" type="xs:string" />
<xs:element name="levelUp" type="xs:string" />
<xs:element name="team" type="xs:string" />
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="userNavigation" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="type" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="actionTime" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="resource" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="name" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="type" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="externalEvent" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="receivedTime" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="message" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="type" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="sender" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
```



```
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="feedback" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="message" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="severity" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="notificationTime" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="type" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="question" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="answer" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
<xs:element name="survey" maxOccurs="unbounded">
  <xs:complexType>
    <xs:sequence>
      <xs:element name="start" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="stop" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="question" type="xs:string" />
      <xs:element name="answer" type="xs:string" />
    </xs:sequence>
  </xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
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</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
```



```
</xs:sequence>
</xs:complexType>
</xs:element>
</xs:schema>
```

10.2 AUDIT XML FILE EXAMPLE

This example describes the training session data related to a procedure containing an operation, a step and three actions.

10.2.1 Session

In the session nodes are specified the execution date, the logged user, the environment and the environment specific data. The session node also contains the procedure nodes (training sessions may have multiple procedure to be completed) as child elements

10.2.2 Procedure

The procedure nodes contain the current procedure's id, start and stop timestamps and all the operations nodes as their child elements.

10.2.3 Operation

The operation nodes contain the operation's id, start and stop timestamps and all the steps nodes as their child elements

10.2.4 Step

The step nodes contain the step's id, start and stop timestamps and all the action nodes as their `childs`.

Comment [TR16]: Children or child elements?

10.2.5 Action

Action nodes contain collaboration info, external data requests, external events information, user feedback data, procedure navigation actions, conditions evaluation, resource using, and surveys data.

In the first action *user0* makes an information request to his supervisor (*userX*) and uses the *video0* resource, then he requests the next action.

In the second action there is a request to the CIDEM for a threshold value used in a condition, then there is the actual evaluation of a condition. *User0* uses the *image0* resource and answers to a survey's question, then he requests the next action.

In the third action the *incident detection system* sends a notification regarding a safety issue. *User0* uses *audio0* resource and makes a note about the current action and then ends the procedure.

10.2.6 Example File

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<session>
  <instance>2ca0906b-1501-45e0-8ce1-67ed0c9cdd7c</instance>
  <date>2016-07-12 15:00:00</date>
  <user>
    <id>user0</id>
    <role>trainee</role>
    <experience>novice</experience>
    <department>assembly</department>
    <levelUp>2016-07-12 15:00:00</levelUp>
    <team>team0</team>
  </user>
  <environment>training</environment>
  <training>
    <user>
      <id>userX</id>
      <role>supervisor</role>
      <experience>expert</experience>
      <department>assembly</department>
      <levelUp>2016-07-12 15:00:00</levelUp>
      <team>team0</team>
    </user>
  </training>
  <procedure>
    <start>2016-010-12 15:00:00</start>
    <id>OP0</id>
    <operation>
      <id>O1</id>
      <start>2016-010-12 15:00:00</start>
      <step>
```



```
<id>S1</id>
<start>2016-010-12 15:00:00</start>
<action>
  <id>A1</id>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:00:00</start>
  <collaboration>
    <start>2016-010-12 15:01:00</start>
    <direction>out</direction>
    <type>information</type>
    <user>
      <id>userX</id>
      <role>supervisor</role>
      <experience>expert</experience>
      <department>assembly</department>
      <levelUp>2016-07-12 15:00:00</levelUp>
      <team>team0</team>
    </user>
    <stop>2016-010-12 15:02:00</start>
  </collaboration>
  <resource>
    <name>video0</name>
    <start>2016-010-12 15:02:00</start>
    <type>video</type>
    <stop>2016-010-12 15:02:00</stop>
  </resource>
  <userNavigation>
    <type>next</type>
    <actionTime>2016-010-12 15:02:00</actionTime>
  </userNavigation>
  <stop>2016-010-12 15:02:00</stop>
</action>
<action>
  <id>A2</id>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:02:00</start>
  <externalData>
    <start>2016-010-12 15:03:00</start>
```



```
<request>condition0_threshold</request>
<response>25</response>
<dataProvider>cidem;Settings</dataProvider>
<stop>2016-010-12 15:03:05</stop>
</externalData>
<condition>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:03:06</start>
  <conditionString>Sensor0 > 25</conditionString>
  <value>22</value>
  <forced>>false</forced>
  <provider>Sensor0</provider>
  <stop>2016-010-12 15:03:10</stop>
</condition>
<resource>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:03:12</start>
  <name>image0</name>
  <type>image</type>
  <stop>2016-010-12 15:02:20</stop>
</resource>
<survey>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:05:10</start>
  <question>question0</question>
  <answer>answer0</answer>
  <stop>2016-010-12 15:05:20</stop>
</survey>
<userNavigation>
  <type>next</type>
  <actionTime>2016-010-12 15:05:00</actionTime>
</userNavigation>
<stop>2016-010-12 15:05:00</stop>
</action>
<action>
  <id>A3</id>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:05:00</start>
  <externalEvent>
    <receivedTime>2016-010-12 15:05:10</receivedTime>
```



```
<message>Safety issue in DepartmentX</message>
<sender>incident detection system</sender>
<type>warning</type>
</externalEvent>
<resource>
  <start>2016-010-12 15:05:10</start>
  <name>audio0</name>
  <type>audio</type>
  <stop>2016-010-12 15:05:20</stop>
</resource>
<feedback>
  <notificationTime>2016-010-12 15:10:00</notificationTime>
  <type>note</type>
  <severity>3</severity>
  <message>Need more images</message>
</feedback>
<userNavigation>
  <type>next</type>
  <actionTime>2016-010-12 15:10:00</actionTime>
</userNavigation>
<stop>2016-010-12 15:10:00</stop>
</action>
<stop>2016-010-12 15:10:00</stop>
</step>
<stop>2016-010-12 15:10:00</stop>
</operation>
<stop>2016-010-12 15:10:00</stop>
</procedure>
</session>
```